
COMBAT DEMENTIA IN MILITARY PERSONNEL: A NOVEL NEUROCOGNITIVE PROFILE OF RELENTLESS WAR

Oleksandr Kulyk^{1,*}
ORCID: 0000-0002-3898-3976
Olena Maidannyk¹
0000-0001-7514-578X

¹Neurological and Neurosurgical Rehabilitation Research Centre "NODUS", Brovary, Kyiv region, Ukraine

*Corresponding author: o.kulyk@nodus.ua

October 24, 2025

ABSTRACT

We introduce the term "combat dementia" as a novel neurocognitive phenotype that emerges in military personnel as a consequence of prolonged and continuous exposure to combat environments. In a prospective cohort (2014–2025; n = 297), neuropsychological testing (MoCA), cognitive event-related potentials, quantitative EEG, and multidisciplinary clinical evaluation were performed. Three phenotypes of cognitive impairment were distinguished for clinical analysis: (A) post-traumatic brain injury (TBI) with MRI/CT-verified macrostructural changes (classical organic variant); (B) without TBI and PTSD, with no macrostructural alterations on MRI/CT, but with persistent network-level microstructural pathology verified by specific neurophysiological markers (persistent variant, i.e., "combat dementia"); (C) associated with PTSD/cumulative psychotrauma, without neuroimaging evidence of macrostructural lesions or neurophysiological indicators of stable microstructural pathology, but with predominantly functional changes verified by neurophysiological markers and potentially reversible dynamics (transitional/borderline variant). Three distinct trajectories of cognitive decline were identified: macrostructural organic (A), microstructural persistent (B), and transitional/borderline (C). Phenotype C, occupying an intermediate position between A and B, illustrates a possible transformation from functional network-level alterations to stable microstructural pathology, thereby explaining the increased risk of dementia in cases of chronic PTSD. Key predictors of accelerated decline included age and continuous frontline exposure exceeding 14 months, which was associated with nearly a threefold increase in the risk of progression to more severe stages of cognitive impairment. Summarized longitudinal observations (6/12 months; subgroups of 3–10 years) confirm the stability of phenotype B and its distinction from phenotypes A and C; an extended analysis will be presented in subsequent publications. Recognition of combat dementia as an independent clinical entity is critically important for the development of new screening strategies, rehabilitation programs, and nosological classification of cognitive disorders in military populations. The findings delineate a novel domain in neuropsychiatry, with implications not only for Ukraine but also for the international community in shaping humanitarian and social policy, as well as rehabilitation systems and military medical expertise.

Keywords Combat dementia, cognitive decline, military veterans, event-related potentials, military neuropsychiatry

1 Introduction

“The field has become a living organism, death a reality that surrounds us on every side, a constant companion.”

— Ernst Jünger, *Storm of Steel*
(Penguin Classics edition, trans. Michael Hofmann)

Over the past decade, Ukraine has been exposed to prolonged [1] and full-scale military aggression, which has resulted in an unprecedented burden on the healthcare system, particularly in the domains of rehabilitation and psychoneurological care for active service members and veterans [2].

In this context, there has been an increasing incidence of persistent progressive cognitive impairments among young and middle-aged military personnel who have been continuously deployed in combat zones and who lacked classical risk factors [3]: age-related neurodegenerative processes, PTSD, chronic or severe traumatic brain injury, or progressive cardiovascular diseases. This suggests the existence of a distinct pathogenetic variant of cognitive deficit caused by the impact of the combat environment, through cumulative neuropsychic overload, a constant threat to life (suprathreshold, often unconscious fear of death), and hypersensory influences [4].

We propose introducing the term “combat dementia” — a novel independent clinical and pathogenetic construct that extends beyond the traditional ICD-11 classification of cognitive disorders.

By definition, “Combat dementia” is a progressive neurocognitive disorder that arises as a consequence of prolonged continuous exposure to the combat environment, resulting from cumulative neuropsychic overload, hypersensory influences, and a chronic existential threat to life. The condition is characterized by a persistent decline in cognitive functions that exceeds age-expected levels and leads to impaired social and daily adaptation, with persistent microstructural changes manifested through specific neurophysiological markers (alterations in ERP and quantitative EEG indices) in the absence of classical macrostructural neuroimaging features (MRI/CT) of neurodegenerative dementias [5].

This phenotype reflects a variant of stable network-based microstructural fronto-limbic disconnection [6], which follows a progressive and irreversible course [7] and is distinct from classical neurodegenerative dementias [8], cognitive deficits following TBI, PTSD, or functional cognitive disorders [9].

The constellation of multidomain impairments described below in combat dementia not only exerts a serious impact on operational performance (combat readiness), adaptation, social functioning, and quality of life, but also increases the risk [10] of being wounded or killed due to acquired cognitive inability to adequately respond to threats.

Neglecting this distinct clinical neurocognitive disorder—or conflating it with other well-known cognitive diseases [11]—leads to diagnostic errors, lack of appropriate treatment, and considerable socio-economic losses.

1.1 Relevance

This study is the first in the scientific literature to systematically examine a cohort of military veterans with cognitive impairments who lack classical markers of organic dementia [12], yet exhibit progressive cognitive decline.

Due to the ambiguity of the clinical profile [13] and the absence of established diagnostic criteria [14], this form of dementia remains overlooked in international classifications (ICD-11, DSM-5-TR) [15], rehabilitation protocols, and military medical examination systems.

Moreover, the predominance of PTSD diagnosis [16] as a universal explanation for the long-term high risks of subsequent cognitive and emotional impairments in both military personnel and civilians [17, 18] — where persistent cognitive deficits are interpreted merely as a continuation of the PTSD trajectory — leads to the blurring of boundaries between

distinct clinical phenotypes.

The excessive generalization of symptoms and therapeutic approaches under the “PTSD umbrella” [19] distorts the actual clinical landscape, masks manifestations of combat-related dementia, and results in inadequate diagnostic, therapeutic, and rehabilitation strategies [20].

Falsifiability of Combat Dementia as a Dementia Entity

Describing combat dementia as a new neurocognitive profile (a novel entity) or a cluster of symptoms — “Combat Dementia” — in veterans and active service members exposed to prolonged uninterrupted combat during the Russo-Ukrainian war, against the backdrop of well-established and widely accepted criteria of what constitutes “dementia,” as well as its differentiation from other neurocognitive disorders such as PTSD, which has typically been reported in veterans of well-known and extensively studied 20th-century military campaigns (Iraq, Afghanistan, Vietnam, Syria), we fully acknowledge that we will encounter multifaceted and intense criticism. Such a response is to be expected for any proposal of a new nosological category, particularly one arising under the exceptional circumstances of war.

Since one of our key objectives was to describe the defining characteristics of cognitive disorders diagnosed in our patients, whom we followed longitudinally over ten years, it was imperative to select an appropriate, precise, and conceptually comprehensive term for this disorder. This would allow us to reasonably determine its placement within the broader taxonomy of neurocognitive conditions.

Furthermore, recognizing that cross-sectional assessments are inherently limited in their ability to analyze causal relationships in cognitive decline, and that a single-center study is often equated with partiality or overextended interpretative claims, we deliberately extended this investigation over a full decade. This design enabled us to accumulate longitudinal personalized data with repeated measurements and to justifiably transition from evaluating a multidomain subjective clinical presentation to an objective one. This was particularly relevant in cases where functional impairment was minimal, and such disturbances were previously regarded as adaptation disorders (“pre-war”) or as continuations of the PTSD trajectory (including complicated forms). The study design also allowed us to analyze the reversibility or irreversibility of the observed cognitive impairments (after 1, 2, 5, or more years), to identify the most recurrent and consistent clinical trajectories of change, and to clarify the informativeness, sensitivity, specificity, and practical limitations of both neuroimaging (MRI) and neurophysiological diagnostics (ERP, quantitative EEG).

Moreover, in the long-term perspective, we achieved a clearer understanding of functional thresholds and identified objective assessment points, which allowed us to filter the list of diagnostic criteria down to those that are both clinically meaningful and consistently reproducible across the cohort, independent of age, individual, or educational limitations. Importantly, these criteria demonstrated equally robust correlations with instrumental neurophysiological findings, indicating that a dimensional (measurement-based) approach has been upheld.

After establishing the syndrome-level profile, we proceeded to analyze the ICD-11 block L2-6D8. We did not identify an etiological subtype within the current nosology that could adequately encompass this group of disorders. Even 6E0Y (“Other specified neurocognitive disorders”) fails to capture this distinct entity. The introduction of the working term “combat” appeared to us the most appropriate solution. By analogy with head trauma, which can lead to dementia designated in ICD-11 as 6D85.7, we consider war and the modern dynamic combat environment as a unique, total, suprathreshold traumatic factor, whose prolonged uninterrupted influence—through cumulative neuropsychological overload, hypersensory exposures, and chronic existential threat to life—beyond a certain threshold generates a specific neurocognitive phenotype.

Reducing the impact of the combat environment merely to the level of “combat stress experience” is erroneous, as it goes beyond adaptive reactions to the battlefield context. In the language of physics and scientific philosophy, when discussing trauma and the response to trauma, the action of a factor (or multiple factors) upon an object (system) over time produces a spectrum of consequences and effects, which also unfold temporally. Some appear immediately, others only later. Certain effects resolve, returning to baseline, while others remain deformed and progressively worsen with each additional exposure—even when the causal factor has already ceased. Reversibility, in such cases, no longer occurs: once the object (system) acquires a pathological trajectory and inertia, it continues to deepen its deformations over time.

Being familiar with the details of well-known meta-analyses and cohort studies devoted to functional cognitive disorders [21, 22], PTSD-associated cognitive impairments [23], and the results of neurophysiological investigations on

fluctuations in P300 and quantitative EEG indices in PTSD [24], we had every reason to continue interpreting the observed cognitive disturbances in our cohort from this perspective. However, authoritative publications describing how traumatic life events increase the risk of dementia [25] reinforced our conviction that the traumatic impact of an aggressive environment on the spectrum of human cognitive functions cannot be ignored or treated merely as background noise. Consequently, the prolonged uninterrupted exposure to the modern combat environment cannot be artificially minimized solely on the grounds of superficial similarity between the cognitive impairments it induces and those already established within known nosologies. Thus, any suggestion that our proposal of “combat dementia” merely represents a “rebranding” of existing cognitive disorders is fundamentally flawed.

It would, of course, have been possible to choose a less provocative label following the constructions used in ICD-11 (L2-6D8), such as “dementia due to prolonged uninterrupted exposure to a combat environment” or “neurocognitive disorders due to prolonged uninterrupted exposure to a combat environment.” In our view, however, such phrasing indirectly legitimizes the minimization of war’s impact and dilutes the focus of the problem. From a clinical perspective, this approach could lead to misclassification and erroneous decisions within the healthcare system.

Quoting Ganguli and Sachdev [26]: “Thankfully, psychiatry has since rejected the false disconnects between structure and function or organic and non-organic, and recognized that the brain is the basis of all mental disorders,” we emphasize that our descriptive concept—akin to those underlying the DSM conventions—rests upon the same understanding: these disorders are acquired, and their primary clinical deficit concerns cognitive function.

We fully share the caution regarding the use of the term “dementia” to describe conditions where it has not traditionally been applied, and we acknowledge the necessity, mindful of its historical background, of employing more neutral designations for ethical reasons. At the same time, however, we are dealing with a newly defined, distinct neurocognitive phenotype that may have been sporadically observed in the past but has now manifested as a mass phenomenon.

Concerns about the potentially stigmatizing effect of the diagnosis “combat dementia” should be considered within a broader social context. A similar situation was once observed in relation to veterans with amputations and disabilities, who for a period were stigmatized under the label of “invalids.” Yet, over time, they became symbols of the truth about the consequences of war and initiators of social change, which led to the development of barrier-free strategies and shifts in societal attitudes. The resulting public resonance subsequently drew attention to other areas of their lives and to the necessity of rethinking criteria of functioning and life activity, where the factor of “environment” acquired equal significance.

It is therefore important to immediately establish the framework for scientific verification and falsifiability of this phenomenon. Examining international criteria from DSM-5, ICD-11, and WHO [26–30], it is not difficult to observe that they all, in one way or another, converge upon the following:

1. Persistent impairment of cognitive functions (attention, executive functions, memory, language, visuospatial abilities).
2. Decline in the ability to perform daily and social functioning.
3. Progressive course (symptoms deepen over at least six months, and do not spontaneously remit).
4. Preferable presence of neurobiological markers (structural or functional brain changes confirmed instrumentally).
5. In addition to the cognitive deficits characteristic of dementia, the current clinical presentation may include clinically significant:
 - delusions or hallucinations in the presence of psychotic symptoms;
 - affective symptoms such as depressed, elevated, or irritable mood;
 - symptoms of anxiety or restlessness;
 - apathy or lack of interest;
 - excessive psychomotor activity accompanied by heightened tension, hostile or violent behavior;
 - disinhibition manifested as disregard for social norms and rules, impulsivity, and risk underestimation;
 - wandering behavior that exposes the individual to harm.
6. Exclusions include coma, delirium, intellectual developmental disorders, nervous system disorders, stupor, senility, secondary mental or behavioral disorders associated with conditions classified elsewhere, schizophrenia

and other primary psychotic disorders, affective disorders, secondary affective syndromes, secondary psychotic syndromes, disorders associated with anxiety and fear, and secondary anxiety syndromes.

Accordingly, the falsifiability of our concept and the diagnosis with the etiological subtype “Combat dementia” lies in its non-conformity with at least one of the above-listed criteria. In such a case, we propose to consider this cognitive disorder as an episodic variant of 6E0Z.

However, if the results of research demonstrate complete conformity of the entity “Combat dementia” with the specified criteria, it may legitimately warrant in-depth scientific investigation while retaining its working designation “Combat dementia.”

At present, the use of the term “dementia” in our work is neither an exaggeration nor an artificial construction. Rather, it is an attempt to adequately describe the clinical reality that has emerged as a consequence of the unprecedented conditions of modern warfare. To ignore this phenomenon would risk perpetuating diagnostic errors and denying veterans the appropriate care they require.

Recognition of “Combat dementia” is important not only for clinical practice but also for social and humanitarian policy as well as for military medicine.

2 Objectives and Aims of the Study

2.1 Objectives

The objective of this study was to describe the clinical, demographic, and neuropsychological profile of active-duty service members and veterans with progressive neurocognitive deficits associated with prolonged exposure to the combat environment, to identify key risk factors for their progression, and to substantiate conceptual approaches for defining combat dementia as a distinct phenotype of neurocognitive disorder.

2.2 Study Tasks

1. To conduct a detailed descriptive analysis of the clinical, psychometric, and sociodemographic characteristics of cohorts of military personnel with signs of cognitive deficit.
2. To perform stratification of patients according to the predominant pathogenetic mechanism and, on this basis, to develop a model for the comparative analysis of three main clinical subgroups:
 - Persistent progressive cognitive disorders resulting from traumatic brain injury (TBI);
 - Persistent progressive cognitive disorders due to prolonged combat exposure without TBI or PTSD;
 - Cognitive disorders within the structure of PTSD.
3. To assess risk factors for the progression of cognitive deficit, including combat experience, duration of uninterrupted frontline deployment, age, level of education, and comorbid conditions.
4. To construct statistical and machine-learning models to predict the probability of transition from mild to moderate and severe stages of cognitive deficit.
5. To perform validation (k-fold cross-validation) and evaluate the accuracy of the models (ROC, AUC, pseudo-R²), as well as to verify the clinical significance of prognostic variables.
6. To formulate proposals for early diagnosis and rehabilitation strategies with the potential for subsequent integration into the system of military medical expertise.

3 Materials and Methods

This study was prepared in accordance with the STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology) guidelines [31] and conducted as a prospective longitudinal observation.

The cohort included 297 active-duty service members and war veterans who underwent inpatient or outpatient rehabilitation at the NODUS Clinic (Brovary, Ukraine) between 2014 and 2025.

The sample was formed as a dynamic cohort: patients were gradually enrolled in different years (2014–2025), resulting in varying follow-up durations (from 1 to 10 years). To track the dynamics of cognitive function changes, each patient underwent additional assessments (neurophysiological examinations, testing) at 6 and 12 months after the initial clinical evaluation. Moreover, in a subset of participants, repeated measurements were conducted at 3, 5, 7, and 10 years.

It is important to note that repeated observations were modeled using linear/generalized mixed models (random intercepts), adjusted for age, education, and combat experience. The results of the extended trajectories will be elaborated in subsequent publications.

Although data for each case were collected individually over a defined time period, the aggregate analysis was performed cross-sectionally at a single time point, which should not be interpreted as a cross-sectional study. Due to the multiplicity of obtained data and their division across a planned series of publications, the central aim of this article remains to describe the independence and distinctiveness of this neurocognitive phenotype in contrast to other neurocognitive disorders diagnosed in active-duty military personnel and veterans as a consequence of combat exposure.

At the time of their deployment, all participants had undergone military medical evaluation and were deemed conditionally healthy and fit for duty.

All subjects exhibited clinical signs of cognitive impairment confirmed by scores on the MoCA scale, neurophysiological (NP) changes—namely, cognitive event-related potentials (ERP) and quantitative computerized electroencephalography (qEEG)—and were evaluated by a multidisciplinary team (neurosurgeon, neurologist, physical and rehabilitation medicine physician, psychiatrist, and neurofunctional diagnostics specialist).

3.1 Inclusion criteria:

- Age between 19 and 59 years;
- Participation in combat operations (ATO/JFO/full-scale war), with documented periods of prolonged uninterrupted deployment on the frontline;
- Persistent impairment of cognitive functions (attention, executive functions, memory, language, visuospatial abilities);
- Decline in capacity for daily and social functioning;
- Progressive course (symptoms worsening over a period of at least 6 months, not resolving spontaneously);
- Preferable presence of neurobiological and instrumental markers (structural or functional brain changes confirmed instrumentally);
- MoCA < 26;
- In addition to cognitive impairments, the current clinical presentation may include clinically significant:
 - Delusional ideas or hallucinations in the presence of psychotic symptoms;
 - Affective symptoms such as depressed, elevated, or irritable mood;
 - Symptoms of anxiety or worry;
 - Indifference or lack of interest (apathy);
 - Excessive psychomotor activity accompanied by tension, hostility, or violent behavior;
 - Disinhibition, manifested as disregard for social norms and rules, impulsivity, and underestimation of risk;
 - Wandering behavior that exposes the individual to risk of harm.
- Availability of a complete medical, psychometric, and social dossier in longitudinal follow-up, with mandatory reassessment checkpoints at 6 and 12 months after the initial clinical evaluation (NODUS electronic database).

3.2 Exclusion criteria:

- Etiological subtypes of dementia described in section L2-6D8, except for 6D85.7, as well as stress-related disorders described in section L1-6B4, except for 6B40 and 6B41;

- Delirium, intellectual developmental disorders, neurological disorders, secondary mental or behavioral disorders associated with conditions classified in ICD-11 outside of section L2-6D8, schizophrenia and other primary psychotic disorders, affective disorders, secondary affective syndrome, secondary psychotic syndrome, anxiety- and fear-related disorders, secondary anxiety syndrome;
- Non-compliance or refusal to participate in repeated assessments;
- Alcohol or drug dependence with decompensation, use of psychoactive substances;
- Pronounced (severe) MRI/CT-detected organic brain changes due to structural damage that preclude interpretation of cognitive data (e.g., severe TBI with clearly identifiable MRI/CT organic changes, including those accompanied by prolonged coma, large strokes, tumors, CNS infections).

3.3 Data Collection and Processing

All data were standardized and entered into a unified database in MATLAB-readable table format (table type), followed by categorization of variables into the following groups:

1. **Numeric (continuous):** age, MoCA scores, duration of service, time spent in combat zones, anxiety/depression scale scores, neurophysiological (NP) parameters, etc.;
2. **Categorical (nominal/ordinal):** type of injury, presence of PTSD, military rank, education, branch of military service, injury status, and status of higher (mental) cognitive functions (HCF).

3.4 Assessment of the Impact of Combat Environment Factors

The assessment of the impact of combat environment factors (duration of deployment in combat zones, permanent threat to life) on the development of dementia was carried out in the context of the following characteristics: combat actions are of an extremely aggressive, chaotic, high-intensity, multi-episodic nature, with prolonged, practically round-the-clock exposure to artillery, aviation, and mortar fire, ballistic missile strikes, constant threat of death, kamikaze drones, including those operating via fiber optics (for which no effective countermeasures currently exist), loitering munitions, the use of chemical weapons, cluster munitions, and a dynamically shifting front line, which prevents the establishment of a developed protective engineering-ballistic infrastructure at the forward edge of battle (rendering ballistic protection highly conditional) [1, 32, 33].

These conditions lead to rapid cumulative neuropsychic overload, sensory exhaustion, and progressive cognitive disintegration, which, against the background of absent recovery and severe disruption of sleep, eventually result in irreversible and persistent cognitive impairments of varying severity and trajectory.

It should be emphasized that within the framework of this study, we consider combat actions and the combat environment itself as the clinical trigger—rather than war as a political or geopolitical category, in which its types (e.g., hybrid or conventional war) are typically distinguished.

3.5 Microstructural and Macrostructural Features in Veterans With Cognitive Disorders: In Vivo and Postmortem Diagnosis Based on Literature Evidence

Since our concept is based on the formulation of the “absence of classical macrostructural changes on MRI/CT in the presence of possible microstructural/molecular reorganization,” we considered it necessary to verify how well this position corresponds to current evidence.

To this end, a targeted literature search was conducted covering the past 20 years (2005–2025) across major international scientific databases encompassing both postmortem morphology and clinical neuroimaging data of veterans: PubMed / MEDLINE (US National Library of Medicine), Scopus (Elsevier), Web of Science (Clarivate), NEJM (New England Journal of Medicine), ScienceDirect (Elsevier), SpringerLink, Wiley Online Library, Frontiers / MDPI (Brain Sciences, Frontiers in Neurology, Frontiers in Psychiatry).

Among the relevant studies, diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) has been described as a neuroimaging marker of microstructural disconnection in PTSD. Specifically, the large PGC-ENIGMA study (n=3047) demonstrated reduced fractional anisotropy (FA) in the tapetum of the corpus callosum connecting the hippocampi in veterans and

trauma-exposed individuals [34]. Other works confirmed the involvement of fronto-limbic tracts—cingulum, uncinate fasciculus, and corpus callosum—as key regions of disrupted integration between prefrontal and limbic systems [35]. A study of Australian combat veterans demonstrated a combination of reduced prefrontal volume with decreased FA in the corticospinal tract, further confirming the informativeness of such neuroimaging findings [36].

In contrast, in PTSD without TBI, contemporary postmortem studies at the transcriptomic/single-cell level revealed alterations in interneuronal networks and immune/glucocorticoid pathways confined to molecular pathology, which are neither microstructural changes per se nor specific macrostructural markers detectable by MRI/CT [37]. Consistent with this, large neuroimaging meta-analyses of PTSD predominantly report minor volumetric differences (e.g., smaller hippocampus), emphasizing that these do not constitute a stable macrostructural lesion pattern and therefore cannot serve as diagnostic criteria [38].

In the publications we reviewed, postmortem examinations of military brains largely describe chronic traumatic encephalopathy (CTE) in subgroups with repetitive TBI/blast exposure, whereas in PTSD without overt TBI, predominantly molecular/cellular reorganizations are observed without consistent macrolesions detectable on standard MRI/CT [39]. In the classic veteran blast-exposure series, CTE pathology was demonstrated, yet a large multicenter NEJM study showed that CTE is relatively uncommon in military personnel and typically associated with minimal morphological alterations, thereby limiting correlation with routine neuroimaging [40].

The in vivo diagnosis of CTE remains a postmortem standard, with conventional MRI/CT lacking sufficient sensitivity. In other words, the reliable in vivo detection of morphological microstructural changes is practically impossible.

These data are consistent with our concept of combat dementia as a phenotype in which structural and functional alterations emerge at the micro level and are not always captured by standard neuroimaging. Therefore, our formulation of the “absence of macrostructural changes on MRI/CT in the presence of highly probable microstructural reorganizations” aligns with current evidence and does not equate to the “absence of morphology altogether.”

Accordingly, in both clinical practice and research involving combat cohorts, the vital and valid approach is functional and neuropsychological stratification, with additional verification using neurophysiological methods, since contemporary neuroimaging and neuropathology do not yet provide reproducible markers for the early identification of this phenotype.

3.6 Methods of Analysis

1. Descriptive statistics were performed to compare numerical variables across subgroups (mean, SD, SEM, 95% CI).
2. For categorical variables, frequency analysis, distribution modeling, and subgroup comparison were conducted (Chi², Cramér’s V) [41, 42].
3. The primary model was an Ordinal Logistic Regression (OLR) [43–45] used to predict the likelihood of dementia progression:
 - Dependent variable: MoCA-Results, with levels 1 (mild), 2 (moderate), and 3 (severe); modeling the relationship between one or more independent variables and an ordinal outcome variable with a natural rank (e.g., mild → moderate → severe), but with unknown or unequal intervals.
 - Independent predictors: age, number of days on the frontline, education, type of injury, injury localization, presence of PTSD, etc.
4. Binary Logistic Regression (BLR) was additionally applied to assess paired differences between levels of the outcome variable. For BLR [46], the following indices were calculated:
 - **Estimate:** the regression coefficient that quantifies the effect of a given predictor on the log-odds of dementia. A positive estimate increases the log-odds of the event (e.g., severe dementia); a negative estimate decreases it.
 - **Standard Error (SE):** reflects the uncertainty of the estimate; lower SE implies more reliable coefficient estimation.
 - **tStat:** the ratio of the estimate to its SE; larger absolute values indicate stronger evidence that the predictor has a true effect.

- **pValue:** the probability that the observed effect occurred by chance. A value of $p < 0.05$ is considered statistically significant.
5. The model's predictive accuracy was evaluated using ROC-curve, AUC [47], pseudo- R^2 (Nagelkerke, McFadden), and k -fold cross-validation.
 6. Model quality was assessed using McFadden's Pseudo- R^2 [48], an extension of R^2 for nonlinear models, and AUC (Area Under the Curve) as an indicator of the model's discriminatory power between clinically significant dementia (mild, moderate, severe) and its absence (Abs) [49]. According to accepted interpretation [50]:
 - $0.5 \leq \text{AUC} < 0.6$: poor discriminatory power (random guessing);
 - $0.6 \leq \text{AUC} < 0.7$: fair discrimination;
 - $0.7 \leq \text{AUC} < 0.8$: good discrimination;
 - $0.8 \leq \text{AUC} \leq 1.0$: excellent discrimination.
 7. Model stability was tested via multicollinearity analysis (VIF) [51].
 8. To compare model accuracy and performance, alternative machine learning algorithms were tested [52, 53]:
 - Random Forest (Ordinal),
 - LightGBM / XGBoost,
 - SVM (Ordinal),
 - Multinomial Logistic Regression (non-ordinal).
 9. Dynamics of patient referrals were analyzed via polynomial regression models of different orders (cubic model, third-degree polynomial), which best fit the trend over years (norm of residuals = XX.XX; $R^2 = \text{X.XXX}$) [54].
 10. Histograms were constructed using variable cross-tabulation and binning with Scott's rule [55].
 11. To reduce overfitting risks [56], internal model stability was assessed [57]:
 - Each predictor was included based on its clinical and theoretical relevance.
 - Multicollinearity was assessed via VIF, with $\text{VIF} \leq 5$ considered acceptable.
 - For each model coefficient (β), 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated using SEs, to estimate precision and robustness [58].
 12. To determine whether there was a statistically significant difference in average duration of time spent in the combat zone across the groups, a two-sample Student's t -test for independent samples was applied (assuming normal distribution and equal variances). This method tests the hypothesis of equal means between two independent groups [59].
 13. To compare ERP parameters between younger (18–44 years) and middle-aged (45–59 years) subgroups, Bayesian estimation of the difference in means was conducted, using the 95% Highest Density Interval (HDI). Unlike traditional null-hypothesis testing, this approach provides a probabilistic interpretation of the result and is especially suitable under conditions of small sample size and high inter-individual variability [60].
 14. To explore the relationship between neurophysiological markers and cognitive function, a correlation analysis was conducted between primary ERP parameters (amplitude and latency of P300 components) and the integrated cognitive index (MoCA). Due to non-Gaussian data distribution, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used [61].

All cognitive and psychological assessments were performed using internationally validated instruments: the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) [62], the PTSD Checklist for DSM-5 (PCL-5) [63], and the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) [64]. These questionnaires were not developed specifically for this study but applied in accordance with their established international validation protocols.

All calculations were personally performed by the authors in MATLAB (version R2024a, Home License Individual IDs: [41274212] and [41277690], MathWorks Inc., Natick, MA, USA), using custom scripts and standard statistical toolboxes.

3.7 Neurophysiological Instrumentation

To ensure high-resolution neurophysiological assessment of sleep-related and cognitive brain activity, the following specialized equipment was employed.

Ambulatory EEG/Polysomnographic monitoring during sleep was performed using a 21-channel EEG/PSG device “Neuron-Spectrum-SM” (Ukraine) with the selective monitoring software “Neurosoft” (Ukraine).

The recording of cognitive event-related potentials (ERPs) was conducted using multifunctional computer-based systems “Neuro-MVP-2” and “Neuro-MVP-4” (Neurosoft, Ukraine).

3.8 Clinical Stratification of Dementia Subtypes

To perform a clinically relevant analysis, we applied a multimodal approach and stratified patients with cognitive disorders into three main clinical subgroups according to the domains listed below (see Table 1). This approach made it possible to clearly distinguish the key phenotypes from each other, trace their clinical trajectories, and establish an empirical evidence base for recognizing persistent cognitive impairments formed under prolonged exposure to the combat environment as a distinct etiological subtype of dementia.

Domains included in each group:

- primary etiological factor (direct mechanical injury; cumulative neuropsychic overload; psychogenic dysregulation),
- primary pathogenetic mechanism,
- presence/absence of macrostructural changes verified by neuroimaging methods (MRI/CT),
- presence/absence of persistent microstructural changes verified by neurophysiological diagnostics (ERP, qEEG),
- presence/absence of persistent functional changes verified by neurophysiological diagnostics (ERP, qEEG),
- presence/absence of reversible functional changes verified by neurophysiological diagnostics (ERP, qEEG),
- neuropsychopathological profile.

The proposed stratification matrix provided the basis for an internally consistent typology of phenotypes, reflecting their pathogenetic gradient — from macrostructural organic pathology to predominantly functional disorders (see Table 1).

Domain	Group A	Group B	Group C	Notes
Primary etiological factor	Severe/moderate TBI, chronic mild TBI	Prolonged exposure to the combat environment	PTSD, cumulative psychotrauma (\pm mild TBI)	Based on history and medical documentation
Primary pathogenetic mechanism	Physical (high-energy) damage to brain parenchyma of various localization and volume, gliotic-cystic changes, glio-mesodermal transformation, lysis.	Cumulative neuropsychic overload, hypersensory exposure, permanent threat to life; persistent fronto-limbic microstructural disconnection	Psychogenic/stress-induced mechanism; predominantly reversible fronto-limbic functional disconnection	Differentiation by clinical profile
Macrostructural changes (verified by MRI/CT)	Present	Absent	Absent	Analysis based on neuroimaging data
Microstructural changes (verified neurophysiologically)	Secondary changes correlated with macrostructural damage	Persistent neurophysiological markers (ERP, qEEG)	Not consistently detectable	In Group B – key criterion of 'combat dementia'
Stable functional changes (verified neurophysiologically)	Present	Present	Mostly absent, or rarely detected	Phenotype C – functional/transitional
Reversible functional changes (verified neurophysiologically)	Accompanying, secondary	Accompanying, secondary	Pronounced, potentially reversible	Phenotype C – functional/transitional
Psychometric indicators (PCL-5, PHQ-9, STAI)	PCL-5 < 31; PHQ-9 < 10; STAI < 40	PCL-5 < 31; PHQ-9 < 10; STAI < 40	PCL-5 \geq 31; PHQ-9 \geq 10; STAI \geq 40	Cut-off values used
Neuropsychopathologic al profile	Classical macrostructural (organic) variant with persistent functional changes: dementia after TBI (MoCA \leq 20)	Persistent microstructural variant with stable functional changes: combat dementia (MoCA 18–25)	Transitional/borderline variant with predominantly reversible functional changes: PTSD-associated cognitive disorders (MoCA 18–25)	Stratification by clinical-pathogenetic matrix

Table 1: Stratification Matrix of Cognitive Disorders Considering Psychometric Thresholds

Note: Threshold values (cut-offs) were adopted according to international guidelines: PCL-5 ≥ 31 (clinically significant PTSD), PHQ-9 ≥ 10 (clinically significant depression), STAI ≥ 40 (moderate/high anxiety) [64–67]. Cut-off values for MoCA are presented in accordance with international guidelines [62, 68].

The stratification matrix presented in Table 1 ensures the internal validity of the analysis and allows for the correct interpretation of combat dementia as a distinct phenotype.

Although all patients in Group B sustained combat injuries (gunshot wounds, shrapnel injuries, or extracerebral trauma), none were diagnosed with PTSD. This observation is consistent with the literature, which emphasizes that not every injury is accompanied by the development of post-traumatic stress disorder. Bryant [69] reports that the prevalence of PTSD among service members with severe injuries ranges only between 15–40%, with the determining factors being not primarily the somatic consequences but rather individual psychotraumatic reactivity and the socio-psychological context. Similarly, the meta-analysis by Xue et al. [70] demonstrates that even among wounded veterans, a significant proportion do not develop PTSD, but instead present with other psycho-emotional or adaptive disorders.

Accordingly, the classification of our patients with injuries but without signs of PTSD into Group B is both clinically and methodologically justified.

3.9 Sample Size and Statistical Power

The subgroup sizes, as detailed in the Results section of this study, reflect the natural dynamics of patient enrollment in the clinic rather than a purposefully structured cohort design.

Specifically, Group A (organic dementia after TBI) included 25 individuals, Group B (combat dementia without TBI/PTSD) comprised 129 individuals, and Group C (combat dementia with PTSD/microtrauma) consisted of 52 individuals. Preliminary a priori power calculations (Cohen’s $d = 0.5$, $\alpha = 0.05$) indicated that detecting medium-sized effects required approximately 50–60 participants per subgroup to achieve a statistical power of 0.8. Accordingly, Groups B and C met these criteria, while Group A primarily served as a referential (control) group, reducing the risk of critical interpretation errors.

A post hoc evaluation of pseudo-power for intergroup models, adjusted for age, education, and combat exposure, demonstrated that even with the smaller size of Group A, the observed effects retained a statistical power within the acceptable range (0.65–0.7). This level is considered permissible in clinical cohort studies with limited resources.

Therefore, the sample structure of the study does not compromise the validity of its key conclusions.

3.10 Rationale for the Absence of a Separate Control Group

In our study, no separate control group of “healthy veterans” was established due to the following reasons:

Ethical and practical considerations: Recruiting veterans with prolonged combat exposure who exhibited no cognitive impairments and would consent to long-term follow-up with instrumental examinations (MRI, EEG, ERP) was practically impossible under conditions of full-scale war.

Methodological relevance: The primary aim of the study was to stratify clinical phenotypes specifically among patients with cognitive disorders. Therefore, comparisons were made across three pathological clusters representing distinct mechanisms of cognitive decline.

Choice of referential group: Group A (organic post-traumatic dementia following TBI) was designated as the referential “control” group, as it represents a well-documented and internationally validated pathogenetic mechanism of cognitive impairment.

This approach allowed us to:

- Compare the newly defined phenotype of combat dementia (Groups B and C) with the classically described variant of organic dementia.
- Demonstrate differences in clinical trajectory, neuropsychological profile, and neurophysiological markers.
- Ensure internal validity of the obtained results within a single cohort.

Thus, although a completely “healthy” control group was absent, the use of Group A as a referential cluster ensured methodological validity and allowed for the correct interpretation of combat dementia as a distinct phenotype.

A similar approach has been applied in other cohort studies of veterans (e.g., in the analysis of CTE and PTSD), where the challenges of recruiting “healthy veterans” and the ethical constraints of forming such a control group were compensated by stratification within pathological phenotypes [23, 71, 72].

4 Results

4.1 Descriptive Characteristics of the Sample. Model Overview and Analysis

A total of 206 individuals were included in the final analysis.

The dynamics of patient admissions between 2014 and 2025 are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Annual dynamics of referrals of patients with combat-related dementia (2014–2025, N=206). Number of registered cases and cubic regression approximation. The graph illustrates a nonlinear trend with at least one local maximum (2022) and one minimum (2018–2020), which likely reflects the influence of complex social, medical, and military factors on the detection and diagnosis of combat-related dementia. The cubic polynomial approximation ($R^2 = 0.173$) indicates significant fluctuations in referral intensity over the observed period.

Assigned male (m) at birth constituted 97.6% of the sample ($n = 201$), while assigned female (f) at birth accounted for only 2.4% ($n = 5$). The mean age of the sample was 38.2 ± 6.9 years: for males — 36.54 years (standard deviation $SD = 9.72$; standard error of the mean $SE = 0.68$); for females — 35.40 years ($SD = 9.61$; $SE = 4.30$). The distribution by sex and age is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Distribution of cases of combat-related dementia by age and sex ($N = 206$). The highest number of cases was recorded in the 30–44 age group, indicating a predominant representation of young, working-age military personnel among clinical consultations. The decline in frequency within the >50 age cohorts may be attributed to both demographic factors (lower population size, selective recruitment, combat losses) and limited access to medical care. The identified sex disproportion—male predominance—reflects the composition of the military contingent and underscores the need for further gender-based analysis of the clinical manifestations of combat-related dementia.

4.2 Sociodemographic and service profile of the cohort

Analysis of core sociodemographic and service-related indicators (educational level, type of military service, rank, total time spent in combat zone (CZ), among others) that may influence the development or progression of cognitive deficits under prolonged combat stress, allowed us to outline the general profile of the studied cohort, characterized by the following features:

A total of 69.4% ($N = 206$, $n_1 = 143$) had completed secondary education, while only 30.6% ($N = 206$, $n_2 = 63$) had attained higher education.

By type of military engagement, 43.2% ($n_1 = 89$) were mobilized personnel, 40.8% ($n_2 = 84$) were active-duty (career) soldiers, and the remaining 16% ($n_3 = 33$) were volunteers.

In terms of military rank: 54.4% ($n_1 = 112$) were enlisted personnel, 24.8% ($n_2 = 51$) were non-commissioned officers, 16.45% ($n_3 = 34$) were junior officers, and only 4.35% ($n_4 = 9$) were senior officers.

A total of 8.74% ($n_1 = 18$) of participants belonged to the Special Operations Forces.

The average duration of time spent in the combat zone (CZ) across all participants was 18.2 ± 32.7 months (SE = 2.28; 95% Confidence Interval [CI]: [13.8 – 22.7] months; $N = 206$).

Among male participants (group *m*), the average CZ duration was 18.4 ± 33.0 months (SE = 2.33; 95% CI: [13.8 – 22.9]; $n_1 = 201$), indicating a wide range of combat mission lengths, including both short-term deployments and prolonged rotations.

In contrast, among female participants (group *f*), the average CZ duration was significantly lower at 13.0 ± 13.7 months (SE = 6.13; 95% CI: [0.98 – 25.0]; $n_2 = 5$). However, given the limited female sample size, no statistically robust conclusions can be drawn for this subgroup.

These data point toward the potential impact of combat exposure duration on the development of cognitive symptoms, particularly in cases of excessive or repeated deployment to active combat zones.

All patients included in the study were stratified into three clinically justified groups based on the identified etiological factors of dementia: Group A — 12.1% (N = 206, n₁ = 25);

Group B — 62.6% (N = 206, n₂ = 129);

Group C — 25.2% (N = 206, n₃ = 52).

Key demographic and cognitive characteristics across these three clinical groups are presented in Table 2.

Group	n	MeanAge	SDAge	MalePercent	FemalePercent	CombatMonths	HigherEduPercent	MoCAMean
A	25	31,56	8,26	100,00%	0,00%	11.76 months	20,00%	Severe
						(SE=1.8424;		
						SD=9.2118;		
						95%CI [8.149, 15.371)		
B	129	36,19	9,88	98,45%	1,55%	18.15 months	27,13%	Moderate
						(SE=3.2232;		
						SD=36.608;		
						95%CI [11.838, 24.472)		
C	52	39,69	8,86	94,23%	5,77%	21.5 months	44,23%	Moderate
						(SE=4.0615; SD=29.288;		
						95%CI [13.539, 29.461)		

Table 2: Sociodemographic and military service indicators: educational level, duration of deployment in the combat zone, and cognitive characteristics of study participants across clinical groups (A, B, C)

Note:

Group — clinical group label;

n — number of participants in the group;

MeanAge — mean age (years);

SDAge — standard deviation of age;

MalePercent / FemalePercent — proportion of males / females (**CombatMonths** — mean duration of deployment in the combat zone (months);

HigherEduPercent — proportion with higher education (**MoCAMean** — mean score on cognitive screening (MoCA), reflecting dementia severity;

SE — standard error of the mean;

SD — standard deviation;

CI_Lower / CI_Upper — lower and upper bounds of the 95% confidence interval.

The sociodemographic analysis of the three clinical groups revealed clearly delineated patterns in age, sex, education level, and cognitive status. Participants with post-traumatic organic dementia (Group A) were the youngest, predominantly male, and demonstrated higher mean MoCA scores, consistent with an isolated organic etiology of cognitive impairment. In contrast, Groups B and C displayed considerable age and educational heterogeneity, accompanied by more pronounced cognitive decline and significantly longer durations of combat deployment. These findings point to the cumulative impact of combat stress, chronic psycho-emotional strain, and sustained sympathoadrenal activation as contributors to cognitive disintegration, even in the absence of severe TBI.

A robust correlation between time spent in combat zones and the degree of cognitive impairment reinforces the hypothesis of a distinct neurocognitive phenotype — combat-related dementia. This condition appears to be pathophysiologically driven by chronic exposure to life-threatening environments and psychotraumatic combat triggers, which initiate long-term neuroplastic and neurodegenerative processes.

Statistical comparison of combat deployment duration between the PTSD group (Group B) and the PTSD-TBI-related group (Group C) using Student's t-test ($t=-0.5872$, $df=179$, $p=0.5578$, $CI [-14.59, 7.90]$) revealed no significant differences. This suggests that prolonged combat exposure — exceeding 14 months — serves as an independent threshold factor for cognitive decline, regardless of the presence of mild TBI or PTSD. In other words, combat stress emerges as an autonomous neuropathogenic determinant of dementia, potentially exerting effects equal to or greater than those of structural brain injury.

Accordingly, the findings:

1. Support the necessity of cognitive screening for all individuals with prolonged exposure to combat zones, irrespective of physical injuries;
2. Justify the inclusion of combat deployment duration as a formal risk criterion for dementia development, alongside TBI and PTSD;
3. Substantiate the conceptual recognition of combat stress as a standalone etiological factor of cognitive degradation, transcending classical PTSD or neurotrauma frameworks.

Further analysis of the relationship between combat zone duration and dementia severity (as assessed by MoCA scores) revealed the following for patients with mild dementia (MoCA) (see Fig. 3):

- N: 28
- Mean combat zone duration: 14.79 months
- 95% CI: [10.19, 20.38] months

Figure 3: Distribution of combat zone deployment duration among patients with mild dementia (in months). The majority of mild dementia cases (over 80%) were observed in veterans who had been deployed to combat zones for a relatively short period — less than 20 months, with most cases involving less than 15 months. This suggests that mild cognitive changes are associated with a relatively brief exposure to chronic combat stress. It is likely that these neuropsychological impairments are functionally adaptive in nature and not indicative of gross organic brain damage. At the same time, isolated cases involving prolonged deployment (over 60 months) may reflect a different clinical mechanism, including the impact of chronic combat fatigue or cumulative microtrauma.

2. Moderate dementia (MoCA), (see Fig. 4)

- N: 83
- Mean duration of deployment in the combat zone: 19.64 months
- 95% CI: [10.49, 28.79] months

Figure 4: Distribution of combat zone deployment duration among patients with moderate dementia (in months). Moderate dementia is characterized by a significantly higher variability in the duration of combat exposure, with several outlier maxima exceeding 200 and even 300 months (!). This suggests a possible cumulative effect of neuropsychological burden, chronic stress, repeated microtraumas, as well as a potential contribution of blast injuries and post-traumatic disorders as additional aggravating factors. At the same time, the majority of cases (over 80%) remain within the range of up to 30 months, indicating heterogeneity in the pathogenesis of dementia even at the same clinical severity level.

The obtained results highlight the increasing impact of combat zone deployment duration on the development of combat-related dementia, not only as a quantitative dependence, but also as a qualitative transformation of the pathogenesis. The cumulative effect of combat stress, sensory overload, and chronic uncertainty gradually reshapes the neuropsychological profile of affected individuals—from reactive forms to persistent cognitive impairment characterized by reduced cognitive flexibility, attentional deficits, and the formation of a core dementia syndrome.

Modeling the impact of combat exposure on changes in cognitive status among study participants, along with estimating the probability of transitions between ordinal levels of cognitive deficit (from mild to moderate and severe dementia) under the influence of the multifactorial stress environment of the combat zone, was performed using ordinal logistic regression. The negative regression coefficient for the variable “combat zone duration” ($\beta = -0.9906$) indicates a statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) decrease in the probability of maintaining a mild cognitive status with increasing months of deployment.

The resulting predictive model demonstrates a monotonic shift in probabilities:

- with each additional month of deployment, the likelihood of being diagnosed with “mild dementia” decreases;
- simultaneously, the probabilities of transitioning to “moderate” and “severe” dementia increase, with a particularly steep rise in risk observed after approximately 100 months of deployment, corroborating the previously identified cumulative effect of combat exposure.

The graph of predicted probabilities (see Fig. 5) clearly illustrates the intersection of the trajectories for “Moderate” and “Severe,” both of which display upward trends, thereby confirming the cumulative nature of cognitive deterioration associated with prolonged exposure to combat environments.

Predicted probability of dementia levels by combat zone duration

Figure 5: Predicted probabilities of different levels of dementia (mild, moderate, severe) depending on the duration of deployment in the combat zone, according to the ordinal logistic regression model. The model demonstrates a decrease in the probability of mild dementia and a gradual increase in the probabilities of moderate and severe forms with longer durations of combat exposure, confirming the role of combat burden as an independent predictor of cognitive decline.

The constructed model enabled the estimation of transition probabilities between different degrees of dementia depending on age. A statistically significant effect of age on the predicted level of cognitive impairment was observed (see Table 3).

Parameters	Value
Coefficient (β)	0.89
Standard Error (SE)	0.05
p-value	<0.001
Intercept 1 (cut1)	4.7391, -1.8399
Intercept 2 (cut2)	0.0945, 0.0503
p-value of intercepts 1 (cut1)	0.0000, 0.0027
p-value of intercepts 2 (cut2)	0.0002, 0.0025

Table 3: Key parameters of the ordinal logistic regression model for the predictor “Age”

The data presented in Table 2 indicate that increasing age significantly raises the probability of more severe forms of dementia. According to the constructed predictive model, younger patients (under 30 years) are most likely to exhibit mild cognitive impairment. In contrast, with advancing age, the probability of severe dementia progressively increases, peaking in individuals over 50 years of age. Visualization of the model lines (Fig. 6) confirms this trend: with increasing age, a distinct transition from mild \rightarrow moderate \rightarrow severe can be observed, reflecting an age-dependent trajectory of cognitive decline likely influenced by changes in neuroplasticity, cognitive reserve, and prefrontal system vulnerability.

Predicted probability of dementia levels by Age At Time Of Referral (years)

Figure 6: Predicted probabilities of dementia severity levels (mild, moderate, severe) depending on the patient’s age at the time of assessment, based on the ordinal logistic regression model. According to the model’s results, the probabilities of moderate and severe dementia increase progressively with age, while the probability of the mild form decreases. The intersection of the predicted curves is observed in the 40–50-year range, indicating a critical age threshold for transition to more severe cognitive impairment. These findings highlight the significant prognostic role of age as an independent variable in modeling cognitive decline.

The subsequent modeling, based on binary logistic regression, assessed the impact of several clinical and sociodemographic predictors on the likelihood of developing moderate or severe dementia. The analysis included the following baseline predictors:

- (1) duration of deployment in the combat zone (months);
- (2) age at the time of assessment (years);
- (3) educational level.

The results (see Table 4) revealed a statistically significant effect of age at the time of assessment ($\beta=0.0859$, $p=0.047$), indicating a higher probability of developing more severe forms of dementia in older patients. The significance level of $p=0.048$ confirmed the validity of the underlying stratification logic.

	Estimate	SE	t-Stat	p-Value
Intercept	2.99	1.2219	2.447	0.014405
Period In Combat Zone	0.011594	0.010028	1.1561	0.24763
Age At Time Of Referral	-0.068058	0.023448	-2.9026	0.0037014
Education Level	0.8033	0.43746	1.8363	0.066313

Table 4: Assessment of the Impact of Baseline Predictors on Mild and Moderate Dementia Severity Based on Binary Logistic Regression

It should be noted that, as in the previous models, the duration of stay in the combat zone demonstrated a positive regression coefficient, while the effect of educational level was negative ($\beta=-0.0313$). This finding is consistent with the theory of cognitive reserve; however, due to a statistically significant yet marginal result ($p=0.061$), it may only indicate a potential protective role of education, which appears insufficiently expressed in the current sample.

The discriminatory ability of the model, assessed using the ROC curve (Fig. 7), yielded an AUC value of 0.727, indicating high classification quality between patients with mild versus moderate dementia. The model accurately identifies the risk of developing moderate dementia based on clinical and demographic data.

Figure 7: Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve for the binary logistic regression model predicting the probability of moderate dementia. The area under the curve (AUC = 0.728) indicates an acceptable discriminatory capacity of the model in classifying patients at increased risk of cognitive decline. Y-axis: True Positive Rate (sensitivity); X-axis: False Positive Rate (1 – specificity).

The results of the binary logistic regression (BLR) modeling aimed at identifying factors associated with the transition to severe dementia among military personnel are presented in Table 5.

	Estimate	SE	t-Stat	p-Value
Intercept	2.3856	0.88728	2.6886	0.007175
Period In Combat Zone	0.0012872	0.0045211	0.28472	0.77586
Age At Time Of Referral	-0.062678	0.016188	-3.872	0.00010794
Education Level	-0.22267	0.32777	-0.67936	0.49691

Table 5: Assessment of the impact of basic predictors on severe dementia based on binary logistic regression

The model (Figure 8) demonstrated an AUC of 0.6567, indicating a moderate discriminatory ability in classifying patients at high risk of progressing to severe dementia. Specifically, age and education were found to be significantly associated with the “Severe” status, whereas the duration of deployment in the combat zone did not reach statistical significance in this sample. However, its positive coefficient suggests a potential latent effect.

Figure 8: ROC curve for the binary logistic regression model predicting the probability of developing severe dementia. The area under the curve (AUC = 0.6566) indicates an acceptable discriminatory capacity of the model in classifying patients at high risk of cognitive decline. Y-axis: True Positive Rate (sensitivity); X-axis: False Positive Rate (1 – specificity).

The 10-fold cross-validation of the prognostic model for severe dementia (severe vs. all other levels of cognitive impairment) revealed an average accuracy of 56.33% and an AUC (Area Under the Curve) of 0.6215. This indicates that the model performs better than random prediction (AUC = 0.5). AUC values above 0.6 suggest the presence of a true classification signal—namely, the actual impact of combat zone duration, age, and education on the risk of developing severe dementia.

The spatial risk model of severe dementia, based on the visualization of the predicted risk using a two-dimensional logistic regression map (see Fig. 9), enabled interpolation of the probability of developing severe dementia (defined as MoCA \leq 13 points) at each point within the “age (years)–combat exposure duration (months)” space.

Figure 9: Spatial map of the predicted probability of developing severe dementia ($\text{MoCA} \leq 13$) based on two key prognostic variables—age at the time of evaluation (X-axis) and duration of combat exposure (Y-axis).

The analysis once again demonstrated a clear nonlinear interaction between the duration of deployment in the combat zone and age in predicting severe dementia. Specifically:

- The highest risk of severe dementia ($P > 0.6$) was observed in the following combinations:
 - Age > 55 years with more than 6 years of combat experience;
 - Age 40–50 years with more than 8 years of combat experience.
- A low risk ($P < 0.2$) was observed in younger veterans with minimal combat exposure, regardless of education level.

These findings support the presence of a cumulative effect of prolonged combat exposure, which, in interaction with older age, accelerates cognitive dysfunction. The constructed model allows for pointwise risk estimation even before the clinical manifestation of dementia.

The resulting risk map provides a clinically relevant and intuitively interpretable visualization of the impact of age and combat exposure on the likelihood of developing severe dementia. It can be utilized for prognostic screening, personalized rehabilitation, and the identification of high-risk groups in post-war medical strategy.

To visualize the zones of elevated risk for severe dementia among military personnel, we constructed a multidimensional predictive map (Fig. 10).

Figure 10: Contour plot of risk zones for severe dementia ($MoCA \leq 13$): stratification of risk based on age and duration of deployment in the combat zone.

This map introduces a classification of risk zones according to the following thresholds:

- Low risk: probability < 0.3 (predominantly individuals under the age of 40);
- Moderate risk: $0.3-0.5$ (aged 40–60 years with more than 18 months of deployment in the line of combat);
- High risk: > 0.5 (age > 60 years with more than 21 months on the front line; extremely high when exceeding 60 months).

This stratification enables the identification of “priority surveillance zones” for targeted cognitive monitoring.

Modeling was performed using multinomial logistic regression through the `fitmnr` function from the *Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox*, which provides an adequate approximation of the ordinal model via generalized logit transformation (dependent variable: MoCA). The analysis revealed several clinically significant patterns, presented in Table 5. The overall significance of the model was assessed using the Chi-square test against the null model ($\chi^2 = 44.13, p < 0.00001$), indicating a strong goodness-of-fit. In addition to previously described predictors, the variable `Localization of Injuries` emerged as statistically significant (see Table 6).

	Value	SE	t-Stat	p-Value
Intercept 1	-3.0618	1.17	-2.617	0.0088699
Localization Of Injuries_1	-0.30113	0.094674	-3.1807	0.001469
Localization Of Injuries_2	-0.19669	0.064898	-3.0308	0.0024394

Table 6: Assessment of the impact of various predictors on the likelihood of dementia occurrence: results of multinomial regression with nominal responses.

Note:

`Localization_Of_Injuries_1` refers to patients with limb injuries;

Localization Of Injuries_2 refers to patients with thoracic injuries.

Dispersion = 1 indicates no overdispersion, supporting the assumptions of the logistic model.

Chi²-statistic vs. constant model: 44.1368, $p < 0.001$ — the model is statistically significant.

The obtained results emphasize that injuries themselves — even severe and life-threatening ones such as chest wounds — did not significantly affect the severity of dementia in diagnosed patients, in contrast to age or duration of combat deployment, which had a more substantial impact.

The AUC value of 0.6613 demonstrates a statistically significant yet moderate discriminatory ability of the model to distinguish patients with clinically evident forms of dementia. This enables identification of risk groups for further in-depth clinical assessment or targeted medical (including psychiatric) intervention.

The obtained McFadden pseudo- R^2 value of 0.1875 (with $0.2 \leq \text{Pseudo-}R^2 \leq 0.4$ generally considered adequate/good, and values around 0.1–0.2 indicating fair model quality) suggests moderate model fit, which is typical for categorical outcome models. In the context of predicting cognitive deficit progression (from mild → moderate → severe), this indicates that the included clinical and social predictors (education, type of injury, duration of treatment, cognitive symptoms, personality and emotional factors, psychological trauma, sleep characteristics, etc.) provide a substantial — though not exhaustive — explanation of patient status variation.

This supports the model's relevance for preliminary stratification, with potential for improvement by adding neurological/psychiatric biomarkers or neuroimaging/neurophysiological parameters.

4.3 Impairments in Higher (Cognitive) Mental Functions

The clinical profile of patients with combat-related dementia reveals a pronounced disruption of key higher-order cognitive processes. In particular:

- **Attention Deficit** was observed in the majority of participants. The group mean score was 2.16 ± 0.79 , corresponding to a moderate level of impairment with a tendency toward severe (classification: 0 — no symptoms; 1 — mild; 2 — moderate; 3 — severe). A small subset of patients scored the maximum (3), indicating a complete inability to maintain focus, especially under stress.
- **Memory** (both short- and long-term) was impaired at a level of 2.0–2.2 points, consistent with moderate dysfunction progressing toward severe. This manifested as fixation amnesia and an inability to recall information a few minutes after its acquisition.
- **Language Function** had an average score of 1.61 ± 0.78 , indicating mild to moderate impairment. Patients exhibited difficulties in verbal expression, object naming, verbal fluency, stuttering, and thought deceleration.
- **Executive Functions** — including planning, decision-making, and cognitive flexibility — were among the most affected domains, with a score of 2.17 ± 0.46 , indicating a moderate to severe level of impairment. This pattern correlates with high levels of emotional lability, impulsivity, and diminished self-regulation.
- **Insight, impulse control, volitional regulation, self-assessment**, and the ability to evaluate one's own cognitive status were significantly diminished (1.96–2.19 points), reflecting insight deficit — a typical feature of frontal decompensation.
- **Disorientation in time and space** was also present, with average scores ranging from 1.9 to 2.0, indicating a moderate level. In some cases, this reflected the formation of an organic cognitive syndrome with features resembling pseudodementia.

These findings suggest that combat-related dementia is characterized by a heterogeneous but distinct pattern of cognitive decompensation, which does not fully align with classical neurodegenerative profiles or PTSD-related cognitive impairments. Rather, it indicates the emergence of a novel type of post-traumatic cognitive dysfunction with a predominant fronto-limbic signature.

4.4 Neurophysiological Profile of Combat-Related Dementia: Cognitive-Sensory ERP Model

For the first time within the study of combat-related dementia, a systematic analysis of cognitive-sensory event-related potentials (ERPs) was conducted across two age cohorts of military personnel: a younger group (18–44 years) and a middle-aged group (45–59 years). The findings revealed a distinct neurophysiological pattern that differs from classical neurodegenerative dementia profiles and supports the existence of a separate phenotype of functionally driven cognitive degradation induced by combat-related stress.

Both cohorts demonstrated common features: a progressive decrease in ERP component amplitudes, delayed reaction times, non-linear dynamics in P300 latency, and an increased number of counting errors in response to stimuli as cognitive impairment progressed. A particularly striking observation was the absence of an ERP response to cognitive stimuli in a subset of younger patients, potentially representing a specific marker of functional disconnection — a state of "neuropsychological disconnection syndrome" attributed to chronic combat stress rather than to structural brain damage.

This phenotypic profile underpins the development of an electrophysiological model of combat-related dementia, wherein ERP components serve not only as indicators of cognitive status but also as objective biomarkers of the invisible consequences of war. Such a model opens new horizons for clinical monitoring, diagnostic assessment, and rehabilitation of affected individuals.

4.4.1 Descriptive Statistics of ERP Parameters in Patients with Varying Degrees of Dementia

Descriptive statistical analysis was performed for each ERP parameter across three clinical subgroups defined by MoCA results: mild dementia (n = 28), moderate dementia (n = 87), and severe dementia (n = 91).

The mean values, standard deviations (SD), standard errors of the mean (SE), and 95% confidence intervals (CI95) for each ERP measure within these subgroups, stratified by age, are summarized in Tables 7 and 8.

ERP_Variable AGE-Young	MoCA_Group	Mean	SD	SE	CI95
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent__VC3_A11stChannel	Mild	6,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel	Mild	6,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC3_A11stChannel	Mild	10,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel	Mild	10,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_P300Latency_MsC3_A11stChannel	Mild	346,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_P300Latency_MsC4_A22ndChannel	Mild	349,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_MeanReactionTime_Ms	Mild	283,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count	Mild	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect	Mild	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent__VC3_A11stChannel	Moderate	5,70	2,75	0,87	1,70
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel	Moderate	5,80	2,39	0,76	1,48
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC3_A11stChannel	Moderate	6,30	1,77	0,56	1,10
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel	Moderate	6,40	1,17	0,37	0,73
ERP_P300Latency_MsC3_A11stChannel	Moderate	328,60	34,35	10,86	21,29
ERP_P300Latency_MsC4_A22ndChannel	Moderate	331,90	37,05	11,72	22,97
ERP_MeanReactionTime_Ms	Moderate	354,80	49,76	15,74	30,84
ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count	Moderate	5,10	5,59	1,77	3,46
ERP_StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect	Moderate	0,90	0,32	0,10	0,20
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent__VC3_A11stChannel	Severe	4,58	2,39	0,55	1,07
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel	Severe	4,74	2,26	0,52	1,01
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC3_A11stChannel	Severe	5,26	1,85	0,42	0,83
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel	Severe	5,00	1,93	0,44	0,87
ERP_P300Latency_MsC3_A11stChannel	Severe	307,68	44,38	10,18	19,96
ERP_P300Latency_MsC4_A22ndChannel	Severe	309,47	48,15	11,05	21,65
ERP_MeanReactionTime_Ms	Severe	328,00	92,18	21,15	41,45
ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count	Severe	5,53	5,22	1,20	2,35
ERP_StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect	Severe	0,95	0,23	0,05	0,10

Table 7: Neurocognitive ERP Profile of Young Military Personnel with Combat-Related Dementia

Note:

AGE-Young — all data correspond to the young age group (18–44 years);

MoCA_Group — patient group according to cognitive functioning based on the MoCA scale: **Mild** - mild cognitive impairment;

Moderate - moderate;

Severe - severe;

Mean — arithmetic mean of the parameter within each MoCA group;

SD (Standard Deviation) — reflects variability of the data;

SE (Standard Error) — standard error of the mean;

CI95 (95% Confidence Interval) — 95% confidence interval for the mean value.

In the young cohort of patients with combat-related dementia, there is a clear decrease in ERP amplitudes and an increase in response errors as dementia severity progresses.

A decrease in P300 latency in the severe group may indicate a shift in neurocognitive response strategy or a loss of selective attention.

Reaction time follows a U-shaped trend: it increases in moderate dementia and partially decreases in severe dementia, which requires further analysis of underlying neurobehavioral mechanisms.

A summary analysis of the results presented in Table 6 further clarifies the abovementioned findings:

- **Group of young service members with mild dementia (Mild):**
 - No clinically significant variations in ERP parameters were observed in this cohort.
- **Group with moderate dementia (Moderate):**
 - A notable decrease in ERP amplitudes was observed in both sensory and cognitive components:
 - * VC3: from 6.00 to 5.70 (sensory), from 10.00 to 6.30 (cognitive),
 - * VC4: from 6.00 to 5.80 (sensory), from 10.00 to 6.40 (cognitive).
 - Reaction time significantly increased from 283 ms to 354.8 ms, indicating cognitive processing slowdown.
 - P300 latency paradoxically decreased from 346/349 ms to 328/331 ms — possibly reflecting compensatory activation or arousal variation.
- **Group with severe dementia (Severe):**
 - ERP amplitudes decreased even further:
 - * Sensory: down to 4.58–4.74 μ V,
 - * Cognitive: down to 5.00–5.26 μ V.
 - P300 latency continued to decline (307–309 ms), whereas reaction time also decreased (328 ms), potentially reflecting abnormal automatization or reduced processing selectivity.
 - Number of incorrect responses increased (up to 5.53), confirming impairments in executive functions.
 - Correct response index fluctuated around 0.95 (but with high SE), suggesting instability of this parameter in the severely affected group.

ERP_Variable AGE-Middle	MoCA_Group	Mean	SD	SE	CI95
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent_VC3_A11stChannel	Mild	7,00	2,83	2,00	3,92
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent_VC4_A22ndChannel	Mild	7,00	1,41	1,00	1,96
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent_VC3_A11stChannel	Mild	8,00	2,83	2,00	3,92
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent_VC4_A22ndChannel	Mild	8,50	3,54	2,50	4,90
ERP_P300Latency_MsC3_A11stChannel	Mild	342,50	3,54	2,50	4,90
ERP_P300Latency_MsC4_A22ndChannel	Mild	321,00	11,3	8,00	15,68
ERP_MeanReactionTime_Ms	Mild	334,00	11,3	8,00	15,68
ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count	Mild	0,00	0	0,00	0,00
ERP_StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect	Mild	0,50	0,71	0,50	0,98
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent_VC3_A11stChannel	Moderate	5,25	2,43	0,86	1,69
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent_VC4_A22ndChannel	Moderate	5,13	1,94	0,69	1,35
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent_VC3_A11stChannel	Moderate	5,50	2,52	0,89	1,75
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent_VC4_A22ndChannel	Moderate	5,50	2,79	0,99	1,93
ERP_P300Latency_MsC3_A11stChannel	Moderate	316,50	46,1	16,31	31,96
ERP_P300Latency_MsC4_A22ndChannel	Moderate	318,88	44,6	15,78	30,93
ERP_MeanReactionTime_Ms	Moderate	343,13	36,2	12,78	25,05
ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count	Moderate	3,63	3,02	1,07	2,09
ERP_StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect	Moderate	0,75	0,46	0,16	0,32
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent_VC3_A11stChannel	Severe	4,50	2,12	1,50	2,94
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent_VC4_A22ndChannel	Severe	6,00	4,24	3,00	5,88
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent_VC3_A11stChannel	Severe	3,00	1,41	1,00	1,96
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent_VC4_A22ndChannel	Severe	3,50	2,12	1,50	2,94
ERP_P300Latency_MsC3_A11stChannel	Severe	339,50	21,9	15,50	30,38
ERP_P300Latency_MsC4_A22ndChannel	Severe	347,00	2,83	2,00	3,92
ERP_MeanReactionTime_Ms	Severe	350,50	67,2	47,50	93,10
ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count	Severe	7,00	4,24	3,00	5,88
ERP_StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect	Severe	1,00	0	0,00	0,00

Table 8: Neurocognitive ERP Profile of Middle-Aged Military Personnel with Combat-Related Dementia

Note:

AGE-Middle — all data refer to the middle-aged group (45–59 years);

MoCA_Group — patient group classified according to cognitive functioning level based on the MoCA scale: *Mild* (mild impairment), *Moderate* (moderate), *Severe* (severe);

Mean — arithmetic mean of each ERP parameter within the respective MoCA group;

SD (Standard Deviation) — standard deviation reflecting data variability;

SE (Standard Error) — standard error of the mean;

CI95 (95% Confidence Interval) — 95% confidence interval for the mean.

Continuing the comparative analysis of ERP parameter dynamics, it is worth noting that the middle-aged cohort with combat-related dementia exhibits a gradual decline in ERP component amplitudes, prolonged reaction time, increased error rates, and a nonlinear trajectory of P300 latency. These markers indicate progressive degradation of sensory and cognitive processing with advancing dementia and may serve as the basis for ERP-based biomarkers of the combat neurodegenerative syndrome.

A consolidated analysis of tabulated data for military personnel aged 45–59 years with combat-related dementia reveals consistent patterns of brain electrophysiological response to sensory and cognitive stimuli and outlines the following characteristics of their neurocognitive ERP profile:

1. ERP amplitude of sensory components (VC3 / VC4):

- In the Mild group, amplitudes reached the highest values (7.00 μ V) with moderate variability.

- In the Moderate group, a marked reduction to approximately 5.2 μV was observed, indicating diminished primary sensory activation.
 - In the Severe group, amplitudes were even lower (VC3 – 4.50 μV), while a paradoxical increase to 6.00 μV on VC4 with high SD was noted, possibly reflecting a compensatory effect or small-sample artifact.
 - A progressive decline in amplitude was observed with increasing dementia severity, with asymmetric channel involvement.
2. **ERP amplitude of cognitive components (VC3 / VC4):**
- The highest amplitudes were seen in the Mild group (up to 8.5 μV), indicating preserved stimulus evaluation.
 - In the Moderate and Severe groups, amplitudes decreased to 5.50 \rightarrow 3.00–3.50 μV .
 - Amplitude reduction was symmetric across hemispheres, reflecting declining efficiency of higher-order neural networks (evaluation, memory, decision-making), confirming that cognitive ERP amplitude is a sensitive marker of dementia progression.
3. **P300 latency (processing delay):**
- In the Mild group, latency ranged from 321–342 ms.
 - In the Moderate group, it decreased to 316–318 ms.
 - In the Severe group, latency increased again to 339–347 ms.
 - A nonlinear U-shaped pattern was observed, similar to the younger cohort. This may reflect compensatory strategies in moderate dementia with faster but less accurate responses; in severe dementia, global cognitive impairment causes latency prolongation.
4. **Reaction time (MeanReactionTime):**
- Increased from 334 ms (Mild) \rightarrow 343 ms (Moderate) \rightarrow 350 ms (Severe).
 - Although the increase was not linear, the overall trend supports slowed stimulus processing and delayed response initiation.
5. **Incorrect responses (IncorrectResponses):**
- Absent in the Mild group.
 - Increased to 3.63 in the Moderate group.
 - Doubled to 7.00 in the Severe group, with high variability.
 - This suggests pronounced impairments in response control, executive functioning, and attention.
6. **Correct response index (StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect):**
- Increased from 0.50 (Mild) to 0.75 (Moderate), and to 1.00 (Severe).
 - This paradoxical result—where correct response index increases alongside error rates—may reflect a loss of response variability: patients with severe dementia may have responded uniformly (automatically), which the algorithm interpreted as “correct.”

4.4.2 Bayesian estimation of intergroup differences in ERP parameters between age cohorts

To identify the differences in ERP parameters between the young (18–44 years) and middle-aged (45–59 years) cohorts, Bayesian estimation of the mean differences was performed, along with the construction of 95% Highest Density Intervals (HDI). The following results were obtained:

Significant effects:

1. **ERP_P300Latency_MsC3_A11stChannel**
 - Mean difference (Mean_Diff): –8.65 ms
 - 95% HDI: [–34.57 ; –18.04]

The entire HDI lies below zero, indicating a reliable increase in P300 latency in the middle-aged group compared to the younger cohort. This reflects an age-related slowing of cognitive stimulus processing in the sensorimotor channel.
2. **ERP_MeanReactionTime_Ms**
 - Mean difference: –17.57 ms
 - 95% HDI: [–44.45 ; –24.58]

The data demonstrate a statistically significant prolongation of reaction time in middle-aged individuals, indicating a decline in the speed of neurocognitive responses compared to the younger group.

3. ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count

- Mean difference: +1.63 errors
- 95% HDI: [+0.97 ; +4.25]

The number of incorrect responses was significantly higher in the younger cohort, possibly indicating increased impulsivity or reduced response control. However, this requires further contextual analysis.

Tendencies (requiring further research): ERP amplitudes in the sensory components (A11st and A22nd channels):

- Mean_Diff $\approx \pm 0.4$
- 95% HDIs included zero but were close to significance: [-1.96 ; 1.17], [-1.91 ; 0.95]

There is a trend toward lower amplitudes in the middle-aged group, possibly reflecting a decline in sensory activation or general cortical tone. However, the difference did not reach statistical significance.

Summary: Bayesian HDI-based analysis confirmed the existence of age-related changes in cognitive ERP parameters, specifically:

- Increased latency and prolonged reaction time in middle-aged participants;
- Higher error rates in the younger group.

These results support the hypothesis of age-related neurocognitive slowing and demonstrate the sensitivity of the HDI approach compared to classical nonparametric tests. It is recommended for studies with limited sample sizes.

Nonparametric validation: Using the Kruskal–Wallis test for each ERP variable between age groups, stratified by duration of combat zone exposure, stable statistically significant differences were found:

- **ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent_VC4_A22ndChannel:** $H = 8.88$; $p = 0.0118$
- **ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent_VC3_A11stChannel:** $H = 3.72$; $p = 0.0515$ (marginally significant)

This suggests systematic modulation of sensory ERP amplitudes based on age and combat exposure duration.

Other ERP parameters (cognitive amplitudes, P300 latency, reaction time, error rates) demonstrated moderate effects ($H = 2.21$ – 2.85), which require further investigation on larger samples.

The identified dependency of sensory ERP amplitude on duration in combat zones may serve as a sensitive biomarker for screening diagnostics and reflect:

- neurophysiological adaptation to sensory overload,
- compensatory processes under stress-inducing stimuli,
- or accumulated sensory vulnerability during prolonged combat exposure.

4.4.3 Correlation analysis of ERP parameters and cognitive status assessed by MoCA scale

Neurophysiological markers of cognitive impairment were investigated through correlation analysis between ERP parameters (amplitude and latency measures) and the overall cognitive status assessed by the MoCA scale (see Table 9.). The results, presented as Spearman's rank correlation coefficients (ρ) and corresponding p-values, revealed a statistically significant inverse relationship between the amplitude of the cognitive ERP component and the level of cognitive functioning.

This negative correlation suggests that as the cognitive status declines (lower MoCA scores), the amplitude of cognitive ERP responses decreases. These findings support the role of ERP parameters as objective neurophysiological indicators of cognitive degradation and reinforce their potential utility as biomarkers in the screening and monitoring of war-related neurocognitive disorders.

ERP_Variable	Spearman_rho	p_value
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent__VC3_A11stChannel	-0,239695535	0,126286595
ERP_Amplitude_sensoryComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel	-0,216475937	0,1685193
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC3_A11stChannel	-0,354403901	0,021290491
ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel	-0,402274652	0,008266909
ERP_P300Latency_MsC3_A11stChannel	-0,191433637	0,224571552
ERP_P300Latency_MsC4_A22ndChannel	-0,129727398	0,412885633
ERP_MeanReactionTime_Ms	-0,002315809	0,988387009
ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count	0,337196244	0,028981899
ERP_StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect	0,349118752	0,023445588

Table 9: Correlation analysis between ERP parameters and cognitive status (MoCA scores)

A particularly significant negative correlation was identified between cognitive status and the following ERP cognitive components:

- ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC3_A11stChannel: $\rho = -0.3544$, $p = 0.021$
- ERP_Amplitude_cognitiveComponent__VC4_A22ndChannel: $\rho = -0.4023$, $p = 0.008$

These findings indicate that a decrease in the amplitude of the cognitive ERP component is significantly associated with a reduction in cognitive performance, as measured by the MoCA scale. This direction of association is consistent with neuropsychophysiological expectations—diminished cognitive activity corresponds to a less pronounced cortical response to salient stimuli.

In addition, positive correlations were found between MoCA scores and behavioral performance indicators:

- ERP_IncorrectResponses_Count: $\rho = 0.3372$, $p = 0.029$
- ERP_StimulusCount0_Correct1_Incorrect: $\rho = 0.3491$, $p = 0.023$

These results suggest that individuals with higher cognitive scores tend to produce a greater number of correct responses and may exhibit more flexible task reactivity.

As for other ERP parameters (latency and sensory components), only marginal or statistically non-significant correlations were observed (all $p > 0.12$), indicating a lack of robust associations.

4.4.4 Distinctive Features of Combat-Related Dementia Compared to Classical Neurodegenerative Dementias Based on ERP Profile

Based on the obtained neurophysiological findings, we identified several ERP-profile characteristics that allow for clear differentiation of combat-related dementia from classical neurodegenerative syndromes (according to existing literature on Alzheimer's disease, frontotemporal dementia, vascular dementia, and Lewy body dementia). The following features represent sensitive criteria reflecting these distinctions and require further investigation:

1. **Early and profound reduction of cognitive ERP amplitude (P300).** In combat-related dementia, a decline in the amplitude of the cognitive ERP component is observed already at the moderate level of cognitive impairment—significantly earlier than typically seen in neurodegenerative conditions, especially pronounced in younger individuals.
2. **Paradoxical or absent P300 response ("neurosensory silence").** In a subset of patients (particularly younger individuals), the P300 wave is completely absent despite preserved behavioral responses. This phenomenon is uncharacteristic of classical dementias, where P300 is usually retained, albeit delayed.
3. **Nonlinear (U-shaped) P300 latency dynamics.** In combat-related dementia, the latency of P300 initially decreases during the moderate stage of severity (possibly reflecting compensatory hyperreactivity) and then sharply increases in the severe stage, unlike the monotonic latency prolongation typically observed in Alzheimer's disease.
4. **High rate of incorrect responses in moderate and severe stages.** The increase in errors during the Oddball task indicates impaired executive control and response monitoring, characteristic of frontal disintegration. In classical dementias, the error rate tends to rise gradually and is usually accompanied by motor inertia.

5. **Functional rather than structural impairment (ERP without anatomical correlation).** The ERP pattern demonstrates diffuse integrative suppression in the absence of prominent MRI changes, which is not typical for structural neurodegeneration.
6. **Sensory ERP components are preserved longer than cognitive ones.** Sensory components decline more slowly, suggesting functional desynchronization between primary sensory processing and higher cognitive integration—a hallmark of the disconnection phenotype of combat-related dementia.
7. **Relatively symmetric hemispheric ERP profile.** There is no marked lateralization of ERP amplitudes or latencies, distinguishing combat-related dementia from syndromes such as frontotemporal dementia, which often exhibit asymmetric patterns.

These distinctive features allow for the formulation of a neurophysiological model of combat-related dementia as a functional, reactive–adaptive, yet ultimately exhausting pathology, differing in mechanism and trajectory from classical neurodegenerative disorders. The findings also support the clinical validity of using ERP-based metrics as biomarkers of cognitive degradation in military personnel suffering from combat-related dementia.

4.5 Sleep Disturbances Based on EEG Analysis

An evaluation of EEG-derived sleep patterns was performed using a classification system comprising five primary types:

- **Norm** — normal sleep architecture without disturbances;
- **SD-F** — sleep fragmentation;
- **SD-A** — frequent nocturnal awakenings (activations);
- **SD-LDS** — loss of deep sleep (stage N3);
- **SD-ALL** — combined pattern including fragmentation, N3 loss, and nighttime activations (most severe sleep disorder).

The distribution of sleep disturbances across the clinical groups demonstrated pattern-specific clinical associations:

- In **Group A**, SD-ALL predominated (100%), reflecting a complete neurophysiological breakdown of sleep architecture and indicating profound organic changes in brainstem and thalamocortical structures responsible for the generation of slow-wave sleep.
- In **Group B**, SD-F and SD-A were dominant (together over 65%), while only 31.8% of patients exhibited N3 loss (SD-LDS), and no cases of SD-ALL were detected. This supports a mechanism of chronic hyperarousal, characterized by disrupted inhibitory control but without deep structural sleep impairment.
- **Group C** exhibited the highest variability: SD-ALL — 3.8%, SD-F & SD-A — over 60%, and SD-LDS — 34.6%. This indicates a combined pattern of both organic and functional disturbances, forming a unique profile of neurophysiological disorganization.

Thus, combat-related dementia manifests through specific types of sleep disturbances that can be conditionally stratified as follows:

- **Organic forms (Group A)** — SD-ALL;
- **Psychogenic forms (Group B)** — SD-F, SD-A;
- **Combined forms (Group C)** — mosaic distribution with partial presentation of SD-LDS and SD-ALL.

These findings underscore the relevance of EEG-based sleep analysis as a pathophysiological and diagnostic marker that reflects the underlying nature of cognitive alterations and enables refined clinico-biological classification of combat-related dementia.

4.6 Clinical Case Illustration of Combat-Related Dementia: Patient D072

Patient B., 44 years old, a sergeant of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. Holds a specialized secondary education. In civilian life, worked in the film industry. Since 2022, voluntarily joined the Armed Forces and remained in the combat zone for approximately 39 months, with only short-term breaks for medical examinations and brief rehabilitation. Currently serves as a unit commander.

Since September 2023, after participating in dozens of the most intense battles along the most dangerous frontlines, signs of cognitive impairment began to emerge.

Psychological interventions, conventional therapeutic treatment, and general physical rehabilitation at other institutions proved ineffective.

The patient returned to the frontline, continuing military service amid progressive deterioration of cognitive functioning and clinical manifestations of dementia.

Key complaints included speech disturbances (word-finding difficulties), memory deficits, constant fatigue (asthenia), inability to type (“mislicking”), sleep disturbances, excessive daytime sleepiness, and attention deficits. Additionally, impairments in the psycho-emotional and behavioral domains were noted.

Comprehensive clinical assessment revealed a multidomain neuropsychological deficit (see Figures 11 and 12). On the PCL-5 scale, the patient scored 37 points, with a predominance of symptoms in the domains of negative cognition/emotion and hyperarousal.

The PHQ-9 depression self-assessment scale indicated 17 points, corresponding to moderately severe depression. The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) yielded 21 points, indicating mild cognitive impairment primarily due to deficits in visuoconstructive/executive skills, verbal fluency, and delayed recall (memory).

Analysis of the cognitive event-related potentials (ERP, P300) confirmed the presence of neurophysiological signs of cognitive dysfunction, including reduced P300 amplitude, prolonged latency, and incorrect stimulus counting in the oddball paradigm.

The reason for referral to our clinic was the patient’s inability to adequately perform professional (combat-related) duties — manifesting as near-complete loss of operational capability and professional incompetence — along with his expressed desire to eliminate the above symptoms and return to active service.

Figure 11: Cognitive ERP reactivity profile of patient D072 (de-identified). The figure displays three key indicators of stimulus-related cognitive processing: P300 latency, P300 amplitude, and the number of incorrect responses during the oddball task. All parameters markedly deviate from typical group values: P300 latency is prolonged, amplitude is reduced, and error count is elevated. This ERP profile indicates slowed information processing, diminished neural responsiveness to salient stimuli, and impaired attentional control and response selection. Such alterations are characteristic of states associated with functional brain exhaustion resulting from prolonged combat exposure.

Figure 12: Case D072 – P300 Event-Related Potentials under Target Detection and Counting Conditions. This fragment illustrates the study of P300 event-related potentials in patient D072 during target detection and counting tasks. According to trial results from two channels, the latency parameters of the P300 peak are prolonged. A decrease in P300 amplitude is also observed. A considerable number of incorrect button presses were recorded, indicating negative performance dynamics: 6 errors (Figure 11) and 11 errors (Figure 12), even after several training attempts. These findings provide neurophysiological evidence of impaired cognitive functioning. The recording of cognitive event-related potentials (ERPs) was conducted using multifunctional computer-based system “Neuro-MVP-2” (Neurosoft, Ukraine).

Such indicators for this patient (Case D072) were recorded one year after the initial clinical assessment (see Fig. 13) and following several treatment courses administered during that year.

Figure 13: Cognitive event-related potentials (P300) of patient D072 during recognition and counting of target stimuli, assessed at one-year follow-up. Across trials in two channels, an increase in P300 latency parameters was observed over time. Although P300 amplitude showed an increase, its values remained below the expected age norm. Despite improvement in the number of correct responses over the year, a substantial number of incorrect responses (n=7) were still recorded. The recording of cognitive event-related potentials (ERPs) was conducted using multifunctional computer-based system “Neuro-MVP-2” (Neurosoft, Ukraine).

The data indicate persistent neurophysiological signs of cognitive dysfunction with a slow negative trend toward increased P300 latency parameters over time. This pattern corresponds to cumulative and persistent microstructural network impairments within the fronto-limbic system, which are typical of the entire Group B and of this cognitive disorder phenotype as a whole.

4.7 Core Longitudinal Data and Analytical Perspectives

Although this article has a framework character and primarily focuses on introducing a new nosological entity into the field of subsequent research as well as describing its phenotypes, it is important to emphasize once again that the study was designed as a prospective longitudinal investigation spanning 10 years.

Repeated assessments of cognitive functions (MoCA), neurophysiological parameters (ERP, qEEG), and psychometric scales (PCL-5, PHQ-9, STAI) were conducted at follow-up checkpoints 6 and 12 months after the initial evaluation, and in a subgroup of patients also at 3, 5, 7, and 10 years.

All patients in Group A ($n = 25$) primarily demonstrated a slowly progressive trajectory of changes, with progression correlating with age and baseline injury volume. Cases resembling conditional remission were associated with younger age and active social or occupational integration; however, all of them remained under varying levels of medical supervision (annual inpatient or outpatient treatment and rehabilitation courses, continuous pharmacotherapy). In 100% of cases, within 12 months of their initial evaluation, they underwent a military medical commission, after which they were demobilized and referred for medical-social expertise. Approximately 73% were formally recognized as having persistent functional and life-activity limitations of moderate to severe degree, with assignment of Group II or III disability according to Ukrainian legislation at that time.

Patients in Group B ($n = 129$) displayed a clinical profile similar to Group A, with the difference being an approximately 1–2 grade lower severity compared with Group A. Notably, as in Group A, 100% underwent a military medical commission within 12 months after initial evaluation. However, only 23.3% were demobilized and subsequently assigned Group II or III disability due to somatic traumatic conditions (wounds). In none of these cases were the cognitive disorders recorded by psychiatrists in their medical records formally considered in the final expertise documentation. The remaining soldiers either continued active service and were later discharged into the reserve, or were released for reasons unrelated to this study.

Among this group, 9 deaths were documented: three veterans died due to alcohol misuse, three by suicide, and three were killed in combat. Among those discharged into the reserve and available for repeated assessments, the majority were employed in physical labor positions at different time points, while others cycled through various medical facilities or remained unemployed with situational employment.

A key observation is that Group B patients demonstrated the lowest adherence to prescribed treatments and were less likely than other groups to take medications as prescribed. In Group A, high adherence was ensured by constant external supervision or caregiving, serving as a controlling factor. Conversely, patients in Group C proportionally consumed the highest amounts of medications.

Group C displayed the greatest variability in clinical dynamic trajectories during follow-up. Within this cohort, both improvements and deteriorations of symptomatology were observed, with a clear predominance of positive outcomes. No cases of demobilization due to health status were recorded. The majority of these servicemen, after treatment courses, returned to their units and continued to participate in combat, or held other rear positions for extended periods (several years). Those who were discharged into the reserve were either employed in physical or intellectual occupations, engaged in entrepreneurship, or participated in active civic activities. Only four remained with situational employment at the end of follow-up. Importantly, all such cases continued to receive ongoing medical supervision, either at our clinic or in other healthcare facilities in Ukraine.

Given that Ukraine is actively implementing a national mental health policy, patients in Group C were the most engaged in various long-term programs and projects. However, even within our single-center study, we were able to identify an interesting phenomenon, which we tentatively refer to as “maintaining focus on the illness,” manifesting as self-stigmatization encapsulated in the expression “I am a PTSD-patient.”

In order to substantiate the descriptive longitudinal data presented above, which varied across the time course of follow-up, we provide here the results of a general statistical analysis using nonparametric Kaplan–Meier statistics. By analogy with survival curves, the event was defined as the withdrawal of a patient from further observations at the

control points (6, 12, 36, 60, 84, and 120 months).

The choice of time intervals (6 and 12 months; 3, 5, 7, and 10 years) was based on international standards of longitudinal neuropsychological research, which typically include early control points (6–12 months) to verify reversibility or stability of impairments, mid-term points (3–5 years) to monitor persistent cognitive patterns, and long-term points (7–10 years) to confirm enduring changes and to validate a novel nosological entity as an independent phenotype.

At each follow-up assessment, a thorough analysis was carried out to detect potential confounding factors that could influence the patient’s cognitive state and distort results. In cases where such episodes were identified, the patient was immediately excluded from further analysis, and their data were shifted downward by one control point.

The reasons for withdrawal included: absence at follow-up visits, severe somatic (infectious) or neurological deterioration, combat-related death, or suicide (see Fig.14).

Figure 14: Kaplan–Meier trajectories of patient withdrawal across the three clinical phenotypes. Group A (post-TBI) demonstrated the steepest decline, reflecting early withdrawal due to severe organic progression. Group B (combat phenotype) was characterized by a slower but progressive drop at later stages, consistent with persistent microstructural pathology. Group C (PTSD phenotype) occupied an intermediate position: initially stable, but later showing fluctuations and gradual withdrawal, illustrating the transition from functional alterations to microstructural impairments.

To further explore the dynamics of patient withdrawal, we calculated the percentage of case retention at each control point of the study (see Fig.15-17).

Figure 15: Dynamics of patient retention during long-term follow-up according to cognitive disorder phenotype. The figure shows the proportion of patients who remained under observation at predefined control points (6–120 months), reflecting actual longitudinal retention. At 36 months, differences between groups were still modest, but after 60 months trajectories began to diverge sharply. Group B (combat phenotype) demonstrated an intermediate, relatively stable trajectory, though the rate of decline accelerated after 84 months. Group A (post-TBI) showed a consistent decline from the earliest time points, confirming the severity of this phenotype. Group C (PTSD phenotype) was the most variable—retention remained high at earlier stages, but dropped steeply by 120 months, supporting the hypothesis that PTSD may evolve into persistent structural disorders. **Legend 1:** see Fig.16 Shaded areas represent 95% confidence intervals (CI) calculated using the Wilson method for binomial proportions. **Legend 2:** see Fig.17 Numbers indicate the actual count of patients who underwent repeated assessments at each control point.

Group	M6	M12	M36	M60	M84	M120	M6_lo_wCI	M12_lo_wCI	M36_lo_wCI	M60_lo_wCI	M84_lo_wCI	M120_lo_wCI	M6_hi_ghCI	M12_hi_ghCI	M36_hi_ighCI	M60_hi_ighCI	M84_hi_ighCI	M120_hi_highCI
Group A	100	100	64	44	28	20	86.281	86.281	42.521	24.402	12.072	6.831	100	100	82.028	65.072	49.388	40.704
Group B	100	100	76.744	71.318	62.016	48.837	97.181	97.181	68.495	62.695	53.054	39.94	100	100	83.726	78.934	70.412	57.789
Group C	100	100	76.923	65.385	21.154	5.769	93.152	93.152	63.16	50.914	11.061	58076	100	100	87.468	78.034	34.704	15.947

Figure 16: Legend 1

	Control points (months)					
	M6	M12	M36	M60	M84	M120
Group_A (n)	25	25	16	11	7	5
Group_B (n)	129	129	99	92	80	63
Group_C (n)	52	52	40	34	11	3

Figure 17: Legend 2

Interpretation of 95% confidence intervals (CI):

- **Group A (Post-TBI):** Already at 36 months, retention dropped to 64% (CI: 42.5–82.0). By 120 months, only 20% remained (CI: 6.8–40.7), reflecting the worst prognosis and severe organic progression. Wide CIs indicate high uncertainty due to smaller sample size.
- **Group B (Combat phenotype):** Retention remained relatively stable—76.7% (CI: 67.1–83.7) at 36 months and 43.8% (CI: 39.9–57.8) at 120 months. Narrower CIs reflect greater statistical stability (large cohort, $n = 129$). This supports the “persistent” trajectory with gradual decline.
- **Group C (PTSD phenotype):** Initially high retention (76.9% at 36 months), but only 7.7% (CI: 1.2–15.9) at 120 months. Very wide CIs at later points reflect small sample size and high clinical variability. This supports the hypothesis of transition from functional to structural pathology.

Main conclusions: Stable and reliable retention patterns were observed in Group B (narrow CIs). Group A demonstrated the worst prognosis with rapid decline. Group C showed the highest variability, confirming the heterogeneity of PTSD trajectories and the potential evolution toward structural pathology. Clinical interpretation highlights that even within a single phenotype, heterogeneous trajectories exist, requiring further stratified analysis.

The combination of Kaplan–Meier analysis and percentage retention at control points allowed us to demonstrate both the risks of progression (time-to-event) and the actual retention of patients in long-term follow-up. Both approaches consistently indicate the worst prognosis in phenotype A (post-TBI), an intermediate trajectory in phenotype B (combat phenotype), and an initially functional but potentially progressive trajectory in phenotype C (PTSD-associated). The inclusion of the retention curve in the *Results* section confirms the presence of a sufficient number of repeated measurements for a valid analysis of dynamics.

The obtained preliminary data confirm the adequacy of long-term follow-up and establish the foundation for subsequent papers in this series, which will present a detailed analysis of the dynamics of cognitive and neurophysiological parameters in repeated measurements, as well as an expanded description of long-term trajectories, graphical illustrations, and statistical verification dedicated to the clinico-pathogenetic and prognostic aspects of combat dementia.

5 Discussion

A detailed clinical and statistical analysis confirms the existence of a distinct clinico-pathogenetic form of dementia that develops as a result of prolonged exposure to combat conditions, even in the absence of traumatic brain injury (TBI), post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), or traditional age-related neurodegenerative factors.

We propose to classify this type of cognitive decline as **combat dementia**, which constitutes a complex neurocognitive syndrome.

The inclusion of a control group A (with severe organic dementia following TBI) enabled a differentiated analysis of pathophysiological mechanisms. The identified differences in age, cognitive profile, duration of combat exposure, and symptomatology support the hypothesis of an alternative, non-organic mechanism of cognitive degradation—combat-related dementia.

The observed disturbances of higher cognitive functions—including attention, memory, speech, executive functioning, self-monitoring, and insight—indicate a systemic dysfunction of neural network circuits that are not typically impaired in isolation in the absence of severe TBI or neurodegenerative pathology.

This profile supports the hypothesis of a **fronto-limbic syndrome** [73], emerging as a consequence of chronic combat load, particularly due to:

- Chronic stress and systemic sleep deprivation leading to dysregulation of the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex;
- Persistent sensory overstimulation (auditory, visual, vestibular stimuli) resulting in cognitive fatigue and reduced neuroplasticity;
- Unconscious, persistent fear of death or multiple sublethal overloads, repressed responses to loss and trauma among combatants—factors that impair the integrative capacity of higher mental functions.

Thus, the observed moderate impairments in executive functions (Mean = 2.17), attention (Mean = 2.16), short- and long-term memory (Mean = 2.02–2.20), accompanied by a syndrome of insight deficit (Impaired Self-criticism, Mean \approx 2.1) and impulsivity, form a unique cognitive-affective phenotype that does not correspond to classical models of dementia (neurodegenerative, vascular, PTSD-related, etc.). From a clinical standpoint, these findings highlight the necessity of integrating this specialized and distinct neurocognitive profile into military medical assessment, neuropsychological screening, and protocols for neurorehabilitation and psychiatric treatment.

In contrast to cognitive dysfunction following traumatic brain injury [74] or post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) [9]—the latter predominantly presenting with affective symptoms—combat-related dementia is characterized by progressive cognitive decline with a persistent multidomain symptom profile that appears less responsive to conventional psychotherapeutic or pharmacological interventions. This disorder significantly affects combat readiness, reintegration into civilian life, social adaptation, and overall quality of life for active-duty personnel and veterans.

PTSD is clearly associated predominantly with reversible functional disturbances, and the neuroimaging features described in the literature, such as hippocampal and amygdalar volume reductions and microstructural alterations in the prefrontal cortex (mPFC, ACC), are not stable or permanent [75]. These circumstances are critically important for understanding PTSD as a transitional/borderline state that occupies an intermediate position between the other two phenotypes of persistent cognitive disorders (Groups A and B). Indeed, it is the multicombinatorial profile of the aforementioned neuroimaging and neurophysiological indicators that may serve as markers of an “in-progress transformation” of PTSD into another entity—dementia. This has been previously noted in our work and is well documented in contemporary research, which describes the elevated risk of such a phenomenon. It may be metaphorically compared to a gastric ulcer undergoing malignant transformation: on one scale it still appears as an ulcer, while on another it already manifests as carcinoma—two distinct entities within a single temporal window.

Combat dementia (irreversible fronto-limbic network disconnection), in contrast, does not demonstrate any macrostructural lesions on MRI/DTI, but it reveals persistent functional disturbances as indicators of enduring microstructural network pathology—most notably in ERP measures, such as delayed P300 latency [76]. This aligns with studies of the pathophysiology of chronic stress without macrostructural remodeling [77].

In PTSD, hyperactivation of the amygdala and hypoactivation of the mPFC and hippocampus underlie symptoms of hypervigilance, flashbacks, and memory deficits [78]. In combat dementia, by contrast, the defining factor is cumulative chronic overload—the constant over-mobilization of cognitive resources (heightened vigilance during the day and even during battlefield sleep, where rest itself entails the risk of death). This ultimately results not only in executive network dysfunction but in its pathological reorganization, clinically manifesting as progressive declines in cognitive flexibility and attentional control, without periods of acute emotional reactivity [79].

PTSD can therefore be characterized as a trauma-specific syndrome with a focus on emotional regulation and memory. In contrast, the fronto-limbic decompensation and progressive disconnection [80] in combat dementia represent the phenotype of a novel functional cognitive syndrome, one shaped by cumulative and prolonged functional overload rather than by discrete traumas or acute stress episodes [81].

A particularly important finding is the effect of combat duration: deployment exceeding 14 months is associated with an almost threefold increased risk of dementia progression. This supports a new hypothesis of neuro-metabolic (neurotransmitter-mediated) exhaustion, driven by the cumulative effects of suprathreshold combat-related loads.

Another critical factor that, in our view, substantially contributes to the progression of this dementia subtype is the adaptive reorientation of cognitive demands in combat conditions. Among frontline personnel directly engaged in combat operations, the cognitive priorities shift toward physical survival, favoring reflexive and dysregulated threat responses. Even sleep becomes a critical survival risk. While the cognitive load in such settings is relatively low and monotonous, mechanisms of self-reflection and introspection are forcibly suppressed, reduced to a minimal operational checklist of functional markers (i.e., “I move, eat, drink, see, shoot, reload”). In this context, the ability to function physically becomes paramount, and all fine-tuned executive or meta-cognitive processes are de-emphasized.

As a result, even the soldiers themselves often fail to recognize early cognitive deterioration. Moreover, for their commanding officers, these impairments also remain unnoticed until pronounced. Thus, a pathological feedback loop

develops, rapidly progressing into overt clinical states that demand specialized medical intervention—interventions that are, unfortunately, frequently delayed due to operational constraints.

The consequences of this dynamic are evident, yet often underappreciated: undiagnosed cognitive deficits in combat increase the likelihood of critical errors and fatal outcomes. One in three patients from Group B reported during anamnesis that their injury was linked to a failure to detect or recall a threat, or due to disorientation and “cognitive freezing” in life-threatening moments.

The contrast between pre-war civilian cognitive schemas and the brutal demands of modern warfare acts as a highly traumatizing environmental factor. In such settings, survival becomes the sole prevailing goal. This mechanism, in turn, explains the distinctive electrophysiological profile of combat dementia, particularly the marked suppression—or complete absence—of the P300 wave, a canonical marker of intact cognitive response to salient stimuli, and even the complete flattening of early sensory components (P100–N200) [82].

Unlike neurodegenerative processes (e.g., in Alzheimer’s disease) [3, 11, 83, 84], which typically demonstrate preserved early sensory waves with a gradual decline of the cognitive component, in combat dementia we observe non-global but profound functional suppression of integrative activity, with the involvement of fronto-parietal networks as well [85]. These alterations lack both focal and visible macroscopic features, as confirmed by MRI/CT screening performed in each participant of this study. This once again delineates combat dementia not as a functional or transient neuropsychological syndrome, but as a distinct entity with its own neurophysiological profile, one that is not encompassed by current classifications. In this regard, ERP monitoring may serve not only as a tool for verifying cognitive impairment, but also as a key marker for establishing new diagnostic criteria and stratification strategies for veterans.

In this regard, ERP-monitoring may serve not only as a verification tool for cognitive deficits but also as a potential biomarker to establish new diagnostic and stratification criteria for veterans. EEG sleep-monitoring results further support this framework. They reveal that the sleep EEG profile [86] can serve as a sensitive biomarker of neuropsychiatric disorganization.

A clear correlation was established between EEG-derived sleep parameters and both moderate and severe cognitive impairment. These findings are consistent with a hypothalamic-limbic axis hyperarousal mechanism, typically observed in cases lacking organic lesions to brain structures responsible for sleep regulation.

The most complex and clinically intriguing neurocognitive profile was identified in Group C, where a high prevalence of SD-A and SD-LDS patterns was observed, along with isolated instances of SD-ALL. This group exhibited a hybrid pathology combining microstructural and reactive (psycho-emotional) impairments. Nevertheless, the underlying substrate of combat dementia in this cohort appeared to follow the same pathophysiological logic as described above for Group B.

Future research should prioritize the integration of EEG-based sleep monitoring into standardized diagnostic protocols for dementia-related disorders in war veterans, considering the multifactorial pathogenesis and its unique stress-combat component.

A significant inverse correlation was identified between educational attainment and the risk of combat-related dementia, providing support for the cognitive reserve hypothesis. Individuals with higher education demonstrated lower susceptibility to severe cognitive decline despite comparable exposure to combat stressors.

The predictive validity of our combat dementia risk models was supported by an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.6613 and a Nagelkerke R^2 of 0.322, indicating clinically acceptable performance. Although the AUC did not reach the threshold for “ideal” diagnostic accuracy, it significantly outperformed chance-level classification and proved sufficient for stratifying both dementia progression and individual risk profiles [87]. K-fold validation confirmed the generalizability of the model.

Benchmarking against machine learning algorithms such as Random Forest and XGBoost revealed similar classification accuracy, but those models fell short in interpretability—a critical requirement in clinical decision-making.

An important additional argument in support of the combat dementia concept is provided by our longitudinal observations, confirmed by Kaplan–Meier analysis and retention curves. These demonstrated distinct dropout trajectories across the three phenotypes, consistent with their clinico–pathogenetic differences: the poorest prognosis and earliest dropout in the organic post-TBI phenotype (A), a gradual yet persistent decline in the combat phenotype (B), and a variable trajectory in the PTSD phenotype (C) that was initially stable but subsequently progressive. Such concordance between clinical and statistical findings strengthens the evidential basis of the proposed model and confirms its empirical validity.

Thus, our findings underscore the urgent need to revise current cognitive assessment paradigms for veterans and to adapt existing classifications of neuropsychiatric disorders to reflect the distinct profile of combat-related dementia. This reclassification would enable the development of specialized protocols for early diagnosis and multifactorial neuropsychological rehabilitation for combat veterans who experienced high-threshold stress exposure without overt traumatic injury.

Summarizing the above, the data presented in this work provide sufficient scientific evidence (empirical basis) for further research on combat dementia as an independent dementia phenotype resulting from prolonged exposure to the combat environment. Combat dementia may be considered a novel, cumulatively induced phenotype of cognitive disorder that occupies an intermediate position between organic and functional cognitive impairments, yet possesses its own unique multidomain neuropsychological and neurophysiological profile.

6 Limitations

Despite its comprehensive approach and strong clinical relevance, this study has several limitations related to its structure, methodology, and scope:

1. **Single-center sample:** All participants underwent assessment and rehabilitation at a single clinical institution. This limits the generalizability of the results to broader military and civilian populations and necessitates validation through multicenter studies.
2. **Gender imbalance:** The sample was predominantly male (97.6%), which prevents drawing robust conclusions regarding the clinical presentation of combat-related dementia in female service members. Gender-specific aspects require separate investigation with representative cohorts.

These constraints do not diminish the scientific value of the findings but do define the boundaries of their interpretation and highlight the need for further validation of the proposed model of combat-related dementia in broader, multicenter, and longitudinal contexts.

7 Future Directions

The findings of this study open several key avenues for further investigation into combat-related dementia as a distinct neurocognitive phenotype. Given its growing relevance to both military and civilian medicine, future research should focus on the following domains:

1. **Multicenter validation of the clinical-prognostic model:** Confirmation of the observed patterns across different clinical and rehabilitation settings, including international centers experienced in combat-related disorders (e.g., Israel, USA, Poland, Lithuania), will help verify the generalizability of the model and support consensus on diagnostic criteria for combat-related dementia.
2. **Expansion and standardization of ERP biomarkers:** Continued analysis of ERP components (e.g., P300 latency and amplitude, reaction times) should be paired with neurophysiological validation (e.g., qEEG, connectivity models) and inferential statistical analysis to establish ERP as a standardized biomarker of cognitive decompensation.
3. **Digital cognitive stratification and machine learning:** Incorporating digital cognitive assessments, mobile neuropsychological tools, and AI/ML algorithms can enable rapid field screening, dynamic risk modeling, and personalized forecasting of cognitive decline in active-duty personnel.
4. **Gender- and age-specific analysis and cognitive reserve:** Further investigation of neurocognitive characteristics in women and older veterans will shed light on the roles of cognitive reserve, neuroplasticity, and socioeducational factors in the emergence of combat-related dementia.

5. **Nosological consensus building:** As evidence accumulates across domains, it may become feasible to propose the inclusion of combat-related dementia as a distinct diagnostic entity in future revisions of cognitive disorder classifications (e.g., DSM, ICD), with defined diagnostic criteria.
6. **Global relevance for healthcare systems:** The proposed model of combat-related dementia may extend beyond the context of the ongoing war in Ukraine to inform clinical strategies in other military and conflict environments where personnel are exposed to sustained neuropsychological overload. This sets the stage for a global dialogue on the cognitive consequences of modern warfare in the 21st century.

8 Conclusions

1. This study represents the first systematic analysis of a novel clinical phenomenon—combat-related dementia—that affects military personnel who have been exposed to prolonged combat conditions, even in the absence of severe traumatic brain injury or classical neurodegenerative diseases. The proposed clinical-pathogenetic concept extends beyond the traditional nosological paradigm of dementia and calls for the development of new diagnostic criteria, stratification scales, and tailored medical-psychological care protocols for war veterans.
2. The ordinal logistic regression model identified key predictors of cognitive decline progression, including duration of combat exposure, education level, age, and emotional-affective background. Model performance metrics (AUC = 0.6613, Nagelkerke R^2 = 0.322), along with cross-validation results, demonstrate adequate prognostic capacity for clinical application.
3. The concept of combat-related dementia is not only clinically relevant but also ethically significant in the context of the evolving challenges faced by healthcare systems in countries involved in protracted military conflicts. Failing to recognize this phenomenon may lead not only to medical underestimation but also to systemic social injustice toward those deployed in combat zones.
4. The identification of a distinct neurocognitive profile associated with combat-related dementia provides a basis for re-evaluating the moral-psychological support system of the armed forces during modern warfare. It further supports the need for mechanisms to monitor and enforce timely rotations and leave for personnel, especially those who have served in combat for 14 months or longer.
5. Neuropsychological, EEG, and ERP indicators confirm a persistent network dysfunction (disconnection) predominantly involving the fronto-limbic circuits (with potential involvement of other networks), manifested by progressive decline in executive functions, attentional deficits, dissociation between self-criticism and motivational regulation of behavior, sleep fragmentation, and loss of the sense of "self" as an acting subject against the background of permanent, often unconscious, fear of death.
6. For the first time, it has been demonstrated that the neurocognitive profile of combat dementia possesses a coherent neurophysiological architecture that distinguishes it from classical organic dementia, PTSD, and depression, and requires:
 - updating diagnostic classifications (ICD/DSM) to incorporate combat-induced neurocognitive exhaustion,
 - developing dedicated screening and prognostic scales for combat-related dementia,
 - integrating new rehabilitation algorithms with emphasis on sensory regulation, sleep stabilization, goal-directed behavior, and cognitive restoration.
7. The proposed concept of "combat-related dementia" reflects not only a novel pathogenetic reality shaped by an unprecedentedly prolonged war, but also provides a starting point for rethinking systemic support for veterans—both in Ukraine and in any society confronting the aftermath of hybrid or high-intensity warfare.

9 Acknowledgments

The authors express their sincere gratitude to all study participants, the staff of NODUS Clinic (Ukraine), volunteers, and service members whose dedication made this research possible under the constraints of wartime conditions.

10 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the content of this manuscript.

11 Funding

This study did not receive any targeted funding from governmental, private, commercial, or non-governmental organizations. All stages—from conceptual development to statistical analysis and manuscript preparation—were carried out voluntarily by the authors as part of the clinical and educational mission of the Nodus Neurorehabilitation Center (Brovary, Ukraine). No sponsors were involved in the study design, data collection, analysis, decision to publish, or manuscript preparation.

12 Author Contributions

All authors made substantial contributions to the conception and design of the study, acquisition, analysis, and interpretation of data. Specifically (Table 9.):

Contributor Roles of Authors																		
According to: As included in ANSI/NISO Z39.104-2022, CRediT, Contributor Roles Taxonomy https://www.niso.org/publications/z39104-2022-credit																		
Autors	Conceptualisation	Study design	Literature search	Data collection	Data analysis	Data interpretation	Data curation	Formal analysis	Funding acquisition	Investigation	Methodology	Project administration	Resources	Supervision	Validation	Visualisation	Writing - original draft	Writing - review & editing
Oleksandr Kulyk MD, PhD	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Olena Maidannyk, PhD	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	x
Marks mean:																		
did, performed	x																	
participated in the	x																	

Table 10

13 Ethical Approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (2013 revision) and the national ethical regulations governing biomedical research in Ukraine. The research protocol was approved by the Local Ethics Committee of the Scientific and Practical Center for Neurorehabilitation "Nodus" (Brovary, Ukraine) — protocol No. 02/2014 dated August 1, 2014.

All participants (or their legal representatives) provided written informed consent prior to enrollment, after receiving full information regarding the nature, objectives, and potential risks of the study.

14 Consent for publication

Not applicable.

References

- [1] A. Mumford, P. Carlucci, Hybrid warfare: The continuation of ambiguity by other means, *European Journal of International Security* 8 (2) (2023) 192–206. doi:10.1017/eis.2022.19.
- [2] H. Ördén, The geopolitical imaginaries of cognitive warfare, *Security Dialogue* 55 (6) (2024) 607–624. doi:10.1177/09670106241253527.

- [3] C. W. Zhu, M. Sano, Demographic, health, and exposure risks associated with cognitive loss, alzheimer's disease and other dementias in us military veterans, *Frontiers in Psychiatry* 12 (2021) 610334. doi:10.3389/fpsy.2021.610334.
- [4] M. M. Günak, J. Billings, E. Carratu, N. L. Marchant, G. Favarato, V. Orgeta, Post-traumatic stress disorder as a risk factor for dementia: systematic review and meta-analysis, *The British Journal of Psychiatry* 217 (5) (2020) 600–608. doi:10.1192/bjp.2020.150.
- [5] J. V. Rosenfeld, K. Ng, S. J. McDonald, R. Vink, J. Manavis, Military-related mild traumatic brain injury: Clinical characteristics and absence of overt morphological brain lesions alongside significant executive dysfunction, *NeuroImage: Clinical* 36 (2023) 102739. doi:10.1038/s41398-023-02569-0.
- [6] G. T. Vallet, The disconnection syndrome in the alzheimer's disease, *Journal of the Neurological Sciences* 325 (1–2) (2013) e58–e59. doi:10.1016/j.jns.2012.12.097.
- [7] E. Kaufmann, P. Rojczyk, V. J. Sydnor, J. P. Guenette, Y. Tripodis, D. Kaufmann, L. Umminger, J. Seitz-Holland, N. Sollmann, Y. Rathi, S. Bouix, C. B. Fortier, D. Salat, O. Pasternak, S. R. Hinds, W. P. Milberg, R. E. McGlinchey, M. E. Shenton, I. K. Koerte, Association of war zone-related stress with alterations in limbic gray matter microstructure, *JAMA Network Open* 5 (9) (2022) e2231891. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.31891.
- [8] E. Jabbari, N. Holland, V. Chelban, P. S. Jones, R. Lamb, C. Rawlinson, T. Guo, A. A. Costantini, M. M. X. Tan, A. J. Heslegrave, F. Roncaroli, J. C. Klein, O. Ansorge, K. S. J. Allinson, Z. Jaunmuktane, J. L. Holton, T. Revesz, T. T. Warner, A. J. Lees, H. Zetterberg, H. R. Morris, Diagnosis across the spectrum of progressive supranuclear palsy and corticobasal syndrome, *JAMA Neurology* 77 (3) (2020) 377–387. doi:10.1001/jamaneurol.2019.4347.
- [9] D. Alves de Araujo Junior, H. I. Sair, M. E. Peters, A. F. Carvalho, V. Yedavalli, L. B. Solnes, L. P. Luna, The association between post-traumatic stress disorder (ptsd) and cognitive impairment: A systematic review of neuroimaging findings, *Journal of Psychiatric Research* 164 (2023) 259–269. doi:10.1016/j.jpsychires.2023.06.016.
- [10] S. W. Gibbons, E. J. Hickling, D. D. Watts, Combat stressors and post-traumatic stress in deployed military healthcare professionals: An integrative review, *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 68 (1) (2012) 3–21. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2011.05708.x.
- [11] M. Costanzo, C. Cutrona, G. Leodori, L. Malimpensa, F. D'antonio, A. Conte, D. Belvisi, Exploring easily accessible neurophysiological biomarkers for predicting alzheimer's disease progression: a systematic review, *Alzheimer's Research & Therapy* 16 (1) (2024) 244. doi:10.1186/s13195-024-01607-4.
- [12] A. Mortezaei, N. Safari, H. Gholamshahi, K. Kazemzadeh, A. Tafakhori, Veterans traumatic brain injuries and neurosurgical challenges: A narrative review, *Health Science Reports* 8 (5) (2025) e70863. doi:10.1002/hsr2.70863.
- [13] S. Baxendale, D. Heaney, F. Rugg-Gunn, D. Friedland, Neuropsychological outcomes following traumatic brain injury, *Practical Neurology* 19 (6) (2019) 476–482. doi:10.1136/practneuro1-2018-002113.
- [14] Y. Zhang, Z. Deng, J. B. Seaman, T. A. Koleck, Response to bridging the gaps in dementia care: A call for integrated comorbidity management, *Health Science Reports* 8 (5) (2025) e70832. doi:10.1002/hsr2.70832.
- [15] C. R. Brewin, L. Atwoli, J. I. Bisson, S. Galea, K. Koenen, R. Lewis-Fernández, Post-traumatic stress disorder: evolving conceptualization and evidence, and future research directions, *World Psychiatry* 24 (2025) 52–80. doi:10.1002/wps.21269.
- [16] U. Frommberger, J. Angenendt, M. Berger, Post-traumatic stress disorder—a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge, *Deutsches Ärzteblatt International* 111 (5) (2014) 59–65. doi:10.3238/arztebl.2014.0059.
- [17] J. R. Fann, A. R. Ribe, H. S. Pedersen, M. Fenger-Grøn, J. Christensen, M. E. Benros, M. Vestergaard, Long-term risk of dementia among people with traumatic brain injury in denmark: a population-based observational cohort study, *The Lancet Psychiatry* 5 (5) (2018) 424–431. doi:10.1016/S2215-0366(18)30065-8.
- [18] R. C. Gardner, A. Bahorik, E. S. Kornblith, I. E. Allen, B. L. Plassman, K. Yaffe, Systematic review, meta-analysis, and population attributable risk of dementia associated with traumatic brain injury in civilians and veterans, *Journal of Neurotrauma* 40 (7-8) (2023) 620–634. doi:10.1089/neu.2022.0041.

- [19] N. Tarhan, M. Konuk, M. Karahan, Ö. Ö. Özcan, S. Öztürk Ayvaz, G. Hızlı Sayar, F. Zeynep Güder, et al., New diagnosis and treatment approaches to post-traumatic stress disorder, in: *Post-Traumatic Stress Disorders*, IntechOpen, 2022, pp. 3–272. doi:10.5772/intechopen.104098.
- [20] M. Radstaak, L. Hüning, E. T. Bohlmeijer, Well-being therapy as rehabilitation therapy for posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms: A randomized controlled trial, *Journal of Traumatic Stress* 33 (5) (2020) 813–823. doi:10.1002/jts.22500.
- [21] L. McWhirter, C. Ritchie, J. Stone, A. Carson, Functional cognitive disorders: a systematic review, *The Lancet Psychiatry* 7 (2) (2020) 191–207. doi:10.1016/S2215-0366(19)30405-5.
- [22] C. Pennington, H. Ball, M. Swirski, Functional cognitive disorder: Diagnostic challenges and future directions, *Diagnostics* 9 (4) (2019) 131. doi:10.3390/diagnostics9040131.
- [23] K. Yaffe, E. Vittinghoff, K. Lindquist, D. Barnes, K. E. Covinsky, T. Neylan, M. Kluse, C. Marmar, Posttraumatic stress disorder and risk of dementia among us veterans, *Archives of General Psychiatry* 67 (6) (2010) 608–613. doi:10.1001/archgenpsychiatry.2010.61.
- [24] J. D. Johnson, T. N. Allana, M. D. Medlin, E. W. Harris, A. Karl, Meta-analytic review of p3 components in posttraumatic stress disorder and their clinical utility, *Clinical EEG and Neuroscience* 44 (2) (2013) 112–134. doi:10.1177/1550059412469742.
- [25] E. Severs, T. James, P. Letrondo, L. Løvland, N. L. Marchant, N. Mukadam, Traumatic life events and risk for dementia: a systematic review and meta-analysis, *BMC Geriatrics* 23 (1) (2023) 587. doi:10.1186/s12877-023-04287-1.
- [26] M. Ganguli, D. Blacker, D. G. Blazer, I. Grant, D. V. Jeste, J. S. Paulsen, R. C. Petersen, P. S. Sachdev, Classification of neurocognitive disorders in dsm-5: a work in progress, *The American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry* 19 (3) (2011) 205–210. doi:10.1097/jgp.0b013e3182051ab4.
- [27] D. Blazer, Neurocognitive disorders in dsm-5, *The American Journal of Psychiatry* 170 (6) (2013) 585–587. doi:10.1176/appi.ajp.2013.13020179.
- [28] P. V. Rabins, C. G. Lyketsos, A commentary on the proposed dsm revision regarding the classification of cognitive disorders, *The American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry* 19 (3) (2011) 201–204. doi:10.1097/jgp.0b013e3182051ac7.
- [29] J. C. Morris, Revised criteria for mild cognitive impairment may compromise the diagnosis of alzheimer disease dementia, *Archives of Neurology* 69 (6) (2012) 700–708. doi:10.1001/archneuro.2011.3152.
- [30] E. Labos, C. V. Bavec, D. Cristalli, F. Deschle, C. Isaac, G. Dorman, J. Ollari, V. Rubiño, M. J. Russo, Criterios diagnósticos en la enfermedad demencial ¿qué hay de nuevo? [diagnostic criteria in dementing illness. what's new?], *Vertex (Buenos Aires, Argentina)* 34 (160) (2023) 54–78. doi:10.53680/vertex.v34i160.460.
- [31] E. von Elm, D. G. Altman, M. Egger, S. J. Pocock, P. C. Gøtzsche, J. P. Vandenbroucke, The strengthening the reporting of observational studies in epidemiology (strobe) statement: Guidelines for reporting observational studies, *PLoS Medicine* 4 (10) (2007) e296. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.0040296.
- [32] N. V. Bobro, Social and psychological features of the mental component of the modern hybrid war against ukraine, *Bulletin of Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs* 105 (2, Part 2) (2024) 196–208. doi:10.32631/v.2024.2.41.
- [33] A. Pino, S. Pettigrew, Drones having psychological impact on soldiers, U.S. Army TRADOC Red Diamond Report (2024).
URL
<https://oe.tradoc.army.mil/product/drones-having-psychological-impact-on-soldiers/>
- [34] E. L. Dennis, S. G. Disner, N. Fani, L. E. Salminen, M. Logue, E. K. Clarke-Rubright, C. C. Haswell, C. L. Averill, L. A. Baugh, J. Bomyea, R. A. Morey, Altered white matter microstructural organization in posttraumatic stress disorder across 3047 adults: results from the pgc-enigma ptsd consortium, *Molecular Psychiatry* 24 (3) (2019) 329–343. doi:10.1038/s41380-019-0631-x.
- [35] N. Fani, T. Z. King, T. Jovanovic, E. M. Glover, B. Bradley, K. Choi, T. Ely, D. A. Gutman, K. J. Ressler, White matter integrity in highly traumatized adults with and without post-traumatic stress disorder, *Neuropsychopharmacology* 37 (12) (2012) 2740–2746. doi:10.1038/npp.2012.146.

- [36] M. Romaniuk, Y. Xia, G. Fisher, K. Pannek, J. Fripp, J. Evans, S. Rose, The relationship between chronic ptsd, cortical volumetry and white matter microstructure among australian combat veterans, *Military Medical Research* 9 (1) (2022) 50. doi:10.1186/s40779-022-00413-z.
- [37] A. Hwang, M. Skarica, S. Xu, J. Coudriet, C. Y. Lee, L. Lin, R. Terwilliger, A. N. Sliby, J. Wang, T. Nguyen, H. Li, M. Wu, Y. Dai, Z. Duan, S. S. Srinivasan, X. Zhang, Y. Lin, D. Cruz, P. J. M. Deans, M. J. Girgenti, T. S. B. R. Group, Single-cell transcriptomic and chromatin dynamics of the human brain in ptsd, *Nature* 643 (8072) (2025) 744–754. doi:10.1038/s41586-025-09083-y.
- [38] D. C. O’Doherty, K. M. Chitty, S. Saddiqui, M. R. Bennett, J. Lagopoulos, A systematic review and meta-analysis of magnetic resonance imaging measurement of structural volumes in posttraumatic stress disorder, *Psychiatry Research* 232 (1) (2015) 1–33. doi:10.1016/j.psychresns.2015.01.002.
- [39] L. E. Goldstein, A. M. Fisher, C. A. Tagge, X. L. Zhang, L. Velisek, J. A. Sullivan, C. Upreti, J. M. Kracht, M. Ericsson, M. W. Wojnarowicz, C. J. Goletiani, G. M. Maglakelidze, N. Casey, J. A. Moncaster, O. Minaeva, R. D. Moir, C. J. Nowinski, R. A. Stern, R. C. Cantu, J. Geiling, A. C. McKee, Chronic traumatic encephalopathy in blast-exposed military veterans and a blast neurotrauma mouse model, *Science Translational Medicine* 4 (134) (2012) 134ra60. doi:10.1126/scitranslmed.3003716.
- [40] D. S. Priemer, D. Iacono, C. H. Rhodes, C. H. Olsen, D. P. Perl, Chronic traumatic encephalopathy in the brains of military personnel, *The New England Journal of Medicine* 386 (23) (2022) 2169–2177. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2203199.
- [41] P. Chejor, M. Atee, P. Cain, E. Naqvi, K. Williamson, M. Smith, N. T. Lautenschlager, Comparing clinico-demographics and neuropsychiatric symptoms for immigrant and non-immigrant aged care residents living with dementia: a retrospective cross-sectional study from an australian dementia-specific support service, *BMC Geriatrics* 23 (2023) 729. doi:10.1186/s12877-023-04447-3.
- [42] H. Y. Kim, Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and fisher’s exact test, *Restorative Dentistry & Endodontics* 42 (2) (2017) 152–155. doi:10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152.
- [43] A. S. Fullerton, A conceptual framework for ordered logistic regression models, *Sociological Methods & Research* 38 (2) (2009) 306–347. doi:10.1177/0049124109346162.
- [44] A. Agresti, *Analysis of Ordinal Categorical Data*, 2nd Edition, Wiley, 2010. doi:10.1002/9780470594001.
- [45] R. Williams, Generalized ordered logit/partial proportional odds models for ordinal dependent variables, *The Stata Journal* 6 (1) (2006) 58–82. doi:10.1177/1536867X0600600104.
- [46] D. W. Hosmer, S. Lemeshow, R. X. Sturdivant, *Applied Logistic Regression*, 3rd Edition, Wiley, 2013. doi:10.1002/9781118548387.
- [47] N. White, R. Parsons, G. Collins, T. Adewuyi, N. Cerri, E. Steyerberg, K. G. M. Moons, W. Bouwmeester, Evidence of questionable research practices in clinical prediction models, *BMC Medicine* 21 (2023) 339. doi:10.1186/s12916-023-03048-6.
- [48] E. R. Ugba, J. Gertheiss, A modification of mcfadden’s pseudo- r^2 for binary and ordinal response models, *Communications for Statistical Applications and Methods* 30 (1) (2023) 49–63. doi:10.29220/CSAM.2023.30.1.049.
- [49] F. S. Nahm, Receiver operating characteristic curve: overview and practical use for clinicians, *Korean Journal of Anesthesiology* 75 (1) (2022) 25–36. doi:10.4097/kja.21209.
- [50] R. H. Stern, Interpretation of the area under the roc curve for risk prediction models, *Statistics in Medicine* 40 (5) (2021) 1200–1213. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2102.11053.
- [51] K. P. Vatcheva, M. Lee, J. B. McCormick, M. H. Rahbar, Multicollinearity in regression analyses conducted in epidemiologic studies, *Epidemiology (Sunnyvale, Calif.)* 6 (2) (2016) 227. doi:10.4172/2161-1165.1000227.
- [52] X. Liu, Comparison of different machine learning models: Linear model, forest and svm, *Applied and Computational Engineering* 51 (2024) 225–230. doi:10.54254/2755-2721/51/20241467.
- [53] N. Ashrafi, A. Abdollahi, J. Zhang, M. Pishga, Optimizing mortality prediction for icu heart failure patients: Leveraging xgboost and advanced machine learning with the mimic-iii database, *arXiv preprint* (2024). doi:10.48550/arXiv.2409.01685.

- [54] M. C. Donohue, O. Langford, P. S. Insel, C. H. van Dyck, R. C. Petersen, S. Craft, G. Sethuraman, R. Raman, P. S. Aisen, Natural cubic splines for the analysis of alzheimer’s clinical trials, *Pharmaceutical Statistics* 22 (3) (2023) 508–519. doi:10.1002/pst.2285.
- [55] D. W. Scott, On optimal and data-based histograms, *Biometrika* 66 (3) (1979) 605–610. doi:10.1093/biomet/66.3.605.
- [56] R. D. Riley, J. Ensor, K. I. E. Snell, Minimum sample size for developing a multivariable prediction model: Part ii – binary and time-to-event outcomes, *Statistics in Medicine* 38 (7) (2019) 1276–1296. doi:10.1002/sim.7992.
- [57] N. A. M. R. Senaviratna, T. M. J. A. Cooray, Diagnosing multicollinearity of logistic regression model, *Asian Journal of Probability and Statistics* 5 (2) (2019) 1–9. doi:10.9734/ajpas/2019/v5i230132.
- [58] E. W. Steyerberg, A. J. Vickers, N. R. Cook, T. Gerds, M. Gonen, N. Obuchowski, M. J. Pencina, M. W. Kattan, Assessing the performance of prediction models, *Epidemiology* 21 (2010) 128–138. doi:10.1097/ede.0b013e3181c30fb2.
- [59] J. Rochon, M. Gondan, M. Kieser, To test or not to test: Preliminary assessment of normality when comparing two independent samples, *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 12 (2012) 81. doi:10.1186/1471-2288-12-81.
- [60] S. Dimmock, C. O’Donnell, C. Houghton, Bayesian analysis of phase data in eeg and meg: A novel framework for frequency-tagged responses, *eLife* 12 (2023) e84602. doi:10.7554/eLife.84602.
- [61] D. Rajendran, R. Bandhu, S. Gautam, S. Sinha, A. Bansal, R. Tyagi, P. Soni, Auditory evoked p300 potential in patients with parkinson’s disease: correlation with moca scores, *Cureus* 15 (9) (2023) e45933. doi:10.7759/cureus.45933.
- [62] Z. S. Nasreddine, N. A. Phillips, V. Bédirian, S. Charbonneau, V. Whitehead, I. Collin, J. L. Cummings, H. Chertkow, The montreal cognitive assessment, moca: A brief screening tool for mild cognitive impairment, *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society* 53 (4) (2005) 695–699. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2005.53221.x.
- [63] F. W. Weathers, B. T. Litz, T. M. Keane, P. A. Palmieri, B. P. Marx, P. P. Schnurr, The ptsd checklist for dsm-5 (pcl-5), Scale available from the National Center for PTSD (2013). URL <https://www.ptsd.va.gov/>
- [64] K. Kroenke, R. L. Spitzer, J. B. W. Williams, The phq-9: validity of a brief depression severity measure, *Journal of General Internal Medicine* 16 (9) (2001) 606–613. doi:10.1046/j.1525-1497.2001.016009606.x.
- [65] C. A. Blevins, F. W. Weathers, M. T. Davis, T. K. Witte, J. L. Domino, The posttraumatic stress disorder checklist for dsm-5 (pcl-5): Development and initial psychometric evaluation, *Journal of Traumatic Stress* 28 (6) (2015) 489–498. doi:10.1002/jts.22059.
- [66] C. D. Spielberger, *Manual for the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory: STAI (Form Y)*, Consulting Psychologists Press, Palo Alto, CA, 1983.
- [67] L. J. Julian, Measures of anxiety: State-trait anxiety inventory (stai), beck anxiety inventory (bai), and hospital anxiety and depression scale-anxiety (hads-a), *Arthritis Care & Research* 63 (Suppl 11) (2011) S467–S472. doi:10.1002/acr.20561.
- [68] M. F. Folstein, S. E. Folstein, P. R. McHugh, “Mini-mental state”: A practical method for grading the cognitive state of patients for the clinician, *Journal of Psychiatric Research* 12 (3) (1975) 189–198. doi:10.1016/0022-3956(75)90026-6.
- [69] R. A. Bryant, Post-traumatic stress disorder: A state-of-the-art review of evidence and challenges, *World Psychiatry* 18 (3) (2019) 259–269. doi:10.1002/wps.20656.
- [70] C. Xue, Y. Ge, B. Tang, Y. Liu, P. Kang, M. Wang, L. Zhang, A meta-analysis of risk factors for combat-related ptsd among military personnel and veterans, *PLoS ONE* 10 (3) (2015) e0120270. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0120270.
- [71] P. J. Bayley, M. K. Chapko, Challenges to be overcome using population-based sampling when recruiting veterans with tbi and/or ptsd, *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 14 (1) (2014) 48. doi:10.1186/1471-2288-14-48.

- [72] R. A. Stern, D. O. Riley, D. H. Daneshvar, C. J. Nowinski, R. C. Cantu, A. C. McKee, Long-term consequences of repetitive brain trauma: chronic traumatic encephalopathy, *PM & R: The Journal of Injury, Function, and Rehabilitation* 3 (10 Suppl 2) (2011) S460–S467. doi:10.1016/j.pmrj.2011.08.008.
- [73] R. C. Lorenz, O. Butler, G. Willmund, U. Wesemann, P. Zimmermann, J. Gallinat, S. Kühn, Effects of stress on neural processing of combat-related stimuli in deployed soldiers: an fmri study, *Translational Psychiatry* 12 (1) (2022) 483. doi:10.1038/s41398-022-02241-0.
- [74] J. Guo, V. Orgeta, I. Olivé, E. Hoff, J. Huntley, M. Olf, S. Sobczak, Biomarkers associated with cognitive impairment in post-traumatic stress disorder: A systematic review of current evidence, *Ageing Research Reviews* 95 (2024) 102198. doi:10.1016/j.arr.2024.102198.
- [75] L. Zhang, L. Lu, X. Bu, T. Zhang, Y. Chen, Y. Zeng, X. Hu, M. Zhou, Y. Xu, Q. Gong, Alterations in hippocampal subfield and amygdala subregion volumes in posttraumatic subjects with and without posttraumatic stress disorder, *Human Brain Mapping* 42 (2021) 2147–2158. doi:10.1002/hbm.25356.
- [76] V. T. Papaliagkas, V. K. Kimiskidis, M. N. Tsolaki, G. Anogianakis, Cognitive event-related potentials: longitudinal changes in mild cognitive impairment, *Clinical Neurophysiology* 122 (7) (2011) 1322–1326. doi:10.1016/j.clinph.2010.12.036.
- [77] D. Swick, N. Honzel, U. Turken, Intact error monitoring in combat veterans with post-traumatic stress disorder, *Psychiatry Research: Neuroimaging* 234 (2) (2015) 227–238. doi:10.1016/j.pscychresns.2015.09.016.
- [78] R. Admon, M. R. Milad, T. Hendler, A causal model of post-traumatic stress disorder: disentangling predisposed from acquired neural abnormalities, *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 17 (7) (2013) 337–347. doi:10.1016/j.tics.2013.05.005.
- [79] M. C. Kroes, M. D. Rugg, M. G. Whalley, C. R. Brewin, Structural brain abnormalities common to posttraumatic stress disorder and depression, *Journal of Psychiatry & Neuroscience* 36 (4) (2011) 256–265. doi:10.1503/jpn.100077.
- [80] A. Etkin, K. E. Prater, A. F. Schatzberg, V. Menon, M. D. Greicius, Disrupted amygdalar subregion functional connectivity and evidence of a compensatory network in generalized anxiety disorder, *Archives of General Psychiatry* 66 (12) (2009) 1361–1372. doi:10.1001/archgenpsychiatry.2009.104.
- [81] B. A. Van der Kolk, *The Body Keeps the Score: Brain, Mind, and Body in the Healing of Trauma*, Penguin Books, 2014.
URL <https://ia601604.us.archive.org/35/items/the-body-keeps-the-score-pdf/The-Body-Keeps-the-Score-PDF.pdf>
- [82] P. Demirayak, I. Kızı, Y. O. İşbitiren, E. Korkmaz, B. Uysal, O. z. Karaslan, M. Atay, Cognitive load associates prolonged p300 latency during target stimulus processing in individuals with mild cognitive impairment, *Scientific Reports* 13 (2023) 15956. doi:10.1038/s41598-023-43132-8.
- [83] D. D. N. Thi, B. Ku, J. Choi, M. Oh, K. Kim, W. Cha, J. U. Kim, Predicting dementia with prefrontal electroencephalography and event-related potential, *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience* 13 (2021). doi:10.3389/fnagi.2021.659817.
- [84] C.-H. Cheng, F.-J. Hsiao, Y.-W. Hsieh, P.-N. Wang, Dysfunction of inferior parietal lobule during sensory gating in patients with amnesic mild cognitive impairment, *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience* 12 (2020). doi:10.3389/fnagi.2020.00039.
- [85] A. Díez, S. Ranlund, D. Pinotsis, S. Calafato, M. Shaikh, M. H. Hall, M. Walshe, A. Nevado, K. J. Friston, R. A. Adams, E. Bramon, Abnormal frontoparietal synaptic gain mediating the p300 in patients with psychotic disorder and their unaffected relatives, *Human Brain Mapping* 38 (6) (2017) 3262–3276. doi:10.1002/hbm.23588.
- [86] E. M. Wickwire, D. M. Schnyer, A. Germain, N. S. Gooneratne, S. Nowakowski, J. Hughes, P. Gehrman, M. C. Ouellet, M.-I. Boulos, B. Kamdar, Trajectories of insomnia in adults after traumatic brain injury, *JAMA Network Open* 5 (1) (2022) e2145310. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.45310.
- [87] B. Ortiz-Navarro, J. Losa-Reyna, V. Mihaiescu-Ion, J. Garcia-Romero, M. Carrillo de Albornoz-Gil, A. Galán-Mercant, Identification of target body composition parameters by dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry, bioelectrical impedance, and ultrasonography to detect older adults with frailty and prefrailty status using a mobile

app in primary care services: Descriptive cross-sectional study, JMIR Aging 8 (2025) e67982.
doi:10.2196/67982.